

Crowdsourcing in cultural heritage

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Executive summary

The aims of this study, within the framework of Common Culture Activity 6, are to:

1. Determine current and planned approaches and practices within the Europeana aggregation ecosystem in relation to crowdsourced metadata and content.
2. Investigate, as comprehensively as possible, past and existing DCH crowdsourcing initiatives across Europe, systematically describing their status and gaining a sound understanding of current practices.
3. Assess the feasibility, desirability and challenges faced in any effort to strengthen the pipeline from such initiatives to enable ingestion of their metadata or access to their content through Europeana.
4. Provide recommendations and guidelines for consideration by Europeana, aggregators and Cultural Heritage Institutions.
5. Support the creation of training materials for the Europeana ecosystem in terms of any agreed interaction with Europeana around crowdsourced assets and deliver this by suitable means (e.g. webinars, Europeana Pro).

The work carried out has involved a 9 month programme (April-December 2020) consisting of desk research, , three online questionnaire surveys (to national aggregators; thematic/domain aggregators and external crowdsourcing initiatives respectively), a series of interviews and three consultative on-line events. The survey data are summarised in extensive annexes.

Crowdsourcing in Cultural Heritage is a broad and heterogeneous concept, defined in this study as ‘the practice of obtaining information or input into a task or project by enlisting the services of a large number of people, either paid or unpaid, typically via the Internet’.

The findings seek to synthesise the main results of the three surveys carried out, with those from the programme of follow-up interviews and the outcomes of the workshops and webinar. It is divided into four sections covering, respectively: Europeana Foundation, national aggregators, thematic and domain aggregators and external crowdsourcing initiatives in Europe.

Conclusions

Perceptions of low value and of a ‘wall’ between crowdsourced digital material and that collected by Cultural Heritage Institutions have diminished considerably, with a stronger sense and evidence emerging that crowdsourced content not only has complementary value in helping understand our culture and history, but also provides a powerful means of engaging communities and the public’s participation in their cultural heritage. Europeana has also played an important role in stimulating crowdsourcing through its several centrally-driven and campaigns on various topics. Several Generic Services projects have also made useful contributions to various aspects.

Nevertheless, the field remains extremely heterogeneous and in the main, it is also necessary for the user to visit the website of each individual external initiative to use its results. The extent of aggregation of content from similar initiatives remains very limited and compares unfavourably with other disciplines where there is a high level of crowdsourcing activity such as natural sciences and biodiversity. Preservation and archiving are also uneven because resource-driven. This is an increasingly serious

problem, since it is likely to have already led to the disappearance or irretrievability of a large amount of valuable digital cultural heritage content.

National aggregators in the Europeana ecosystem have, until now, mainly seen UGC as something outside their main scope or beyond their resources, although this may be beginning to change. Several thematic and domain aggregators have undertaken a patchwork of activities, recognise a need to act and are planning accordingly. At the Europeana Foundation, there is awareness and much discussion of the issues at stake, but the limitations upon the available capacity of technical resources create a difficulty in prioritising what would undoubtedly be a substantial task.

The following Proposals are made.

Aggregation. The first question is whether it is possible to create an aggregation ‘pipeline’ system for User Generated Content, on similar principles to those adopted with success to those used by Europeana in aggregating diverse digital content from CHI. In thinking about this, it could be useful to look in depth at what has been done in other fields, such as natural science/biodiversity and in Citizen Science more generally, how far this has succeeded, whether it could be emulated in cultural heritage and who could lead such an initiative. A current fulcrum would clearly be how the Europeana Data Model (EDM) could be modified and enhanced for greater hospitability to metadata of crowdsourced content and what mappings would be needed.

Guidance and standardisation. Guidance on a more consistent and standardised approach to crowdsourcing between external initiatives could be effective in increasing common practices, technical interoperability and thereby aggregation, increased access and re-use. Furthermore, whether Europeana’s reputation in the field of digital culture could add strength to any such guidance.

Segmenting guidance. Given the heterogeneity of aims, approaches and most other aspects of crowdsourcing initiatives, it would almost certainly be necessary to divide any such guidance according to different types of crowdsourcing, since an attempt to create overarching guidelines would likely result in superficial generalisation and limited utility in practice (and there are, for instance, many available sources on how to organise crowdsourcing events and different types of ‘thons’). Such a segmentation would need to cover User Generated Content, User Metadata Enhancements, Transcription and other main categories of crowdsourcing.

Resourcing the work. Since the production of guidance might well create a strain on the already stretched human resources at EF, the possibility of engaging expertise from within the membership of the Europeana Network Association in a Task Force or other form could be considered. Likewise, a new Generic Services project could address the whole question of an aggregation infrastructure for crowdsourcing.

3D modelling. The tantalising possibility of crowdsourcing data acquisition in support of 3D modelling of Cultural Heritage has been partially realised in several initiatives, but much work remains to develop a consistently adoptable approach. This suggests a possible need for a separate project on this topic.

Quality. Behind everything lie remaining uncertainties about how to assess the quality and value of crowdsourced content and data and how to consider it in the context of what Cultural Heritage Institutions collect. The notion of quality has a number of aspects including technical quality (resolution

etc.), accuracy of metadata inputs, contextual relevance etc. It is as yet unresolved. Initiatives such as the ‘gold, silver, bronze’ approach recently launched by Crowd Heritage are certainly worth taking into account.

1 Introduction and methodology

The aims of this study, within the framework of Common Culture Activity 6 are to:

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4. Provide recommendations and guidelines for consideration by Europeana, aggregators and Cultural Heritage Institutions.
5. Support the creation of training materials for the Europeana ecosystem in terms of any agreed interaction with Europeana around crowdsourced assets and deliver this by suitable means (e.g. webinars, Europeana Pro).

Crowdsourcing in Cultural Heritage is a broad and heterogeneous concept, defined in this study as ‘the practice of obtaining information or input into a task or project by enlisting the services of a large number of people, either paid or unpaid, typically via the Internet’

This Report builds on an Interim Report produced in September on the work carried out has involved a 9 month programme (April-December 2020) consisting of desk research, , three online questionnaire surveys (to national aggregators; thematic/domain aggregators and external crowdsourcing initiatives respectively), a series of interviews and three consultative on-line events.

1.1 Surveys

1. national aggregators in the Europeana Ecosystem which are partners in the Common Culture project. These were shared on the Common Culture and Europeana Aggregators Forum project Basecamp facilities (11 responses)
2. thematic and domain aggregators through the Europeana Aggregators Forum (2 responses)
3. external Cultural Heritage crowdsourcing initiatives identified through the desk research (138 identified – listed at Annex 1 - 107 successfully contacted, 14 responses). Survey 3 was also supported by a social media campaign linking to the survey conducted by Cyprus University of Technology and also promoted through the ENA Newsletter and by the ENA Communicators Community which resulted in a further 13 responses, making 27 in total.

The first two surveys were similar to each other with minor refinements and were designed to gain an overview of current actions and attitudes towards crowdsourcing by aggregators within the Europeana ‘ecosystem’. The third was more detailed and intended to investigate in more depth the extent and types of activity of a range of external crowdsourcing initiatives and projects across Europe. Each of the survey questionnaires used Google Forms.

Reasons for failure to contact identified organisations with the questionnaire were:

- Permission Denied
- Sender Address rejected: Relay Access Denied.
- Online contact forms not working or unable to add URL

1.2 Interviews

In following up the Interim Report and leading to this Final Report, discussions were sought with (1) nominated policy and technical staff at Europeana HQ, (2) national and thematic/domain aggregators who responded to the survey in pursuit of specific questions and some of those who did not respond, (3) a selection of responding external crowdsourcing initiatives in pursuit of specific issues.

Online interviews were held over the period 23 November to 16 December 2020, as follows.

4. Tom Miles, Europeana Sounds, UK
5. Ad Polle, Europeana, EU
6. Alexander Schatek, Topothek Austria
7. Valentina Bacchi, Photoconsortium, Italy
8. Vahur Paik, Ajapaik, Estonia
9. Rosie Brigham, Monument Monitor, UK
10. Nicole Emmenegger, EU Screen, Netherlands
11. Joaquim Santos, Herbarium, University of Coimbra, Portugal.
12. Louise Broch, DR archive, Denmark.
13. Una Bhreathnach, Meitheal Dúchas.ie, Ireland
14. Eva Kaptijn, Heritage Quest, Netherlands
15. Kerstin Arnold, Archives Portal Europe, Germany
16. Adrian Murphy, Europeana, EU
17. Pavel Kats, Judaica, Netherlands
18. Kathryn Cassidy, DRI (national aggregator), Ireland

1.3 Workshops

Online workshops were also organised to take further soundings, in conjunction with two events:

- EuroMed2020 conference (5 November 2020)¹
- CIDOC2020 (8 December 2020)²

1.4 Webinar

The provisional findings of the study formed the basis of a recorded webinar³ organised within the framework of Common Culture on 15 December 2020

¹ <https://www.euromed2020.eu/workshops>

² <https://digitalheritagelab.eu/event/cidoc-online-conference-2020/>

³ <https://pro.europeana.eu/event/crowdsourcing-of-digital-cultural-heritage>

2. Findings

This section seeks to synthesise the main results of the three surveys carried out, with those from the programme of follow-up interviews and the outcomes of the workshops and webinar. It is divided into four sections covering, respectively: Europeana Foundation, national aggregators, thematic and domain aggregators and external crowdsourcing initiatives in Europe.

2.1 Europeana

Europeana Foundation (EF) has played a visible and important role in initiating Cultural Heritage User Generated Content (UGC) crowdsourcing campaigns since 2012, notably those managed under the Europeana Awareness Best Practice Network project, including the World War I and 1989 campaigns. These campaigns were well-resourced and successful in engaging with people to motivate a supply of stories, sustaining interest until long after the project and supporting the case for including privately-owned content in Europeana along with that in the collections of Cultural Heritage Institutions.

This success led to further UGC campaigns such as those on Migration, Work and Sport, funded variously within DSI and Generic Services projects. With fewer human resources and technical support available these, in the main, have proved more difficult to maintain centrally, generating less content than those in Europeana Awareness, although the WW1 campaign had a longer duration and extended through successor projects such as DSI and Enrich Europeana.

Further investments have been made to engage with audiences in order to improve disclosure of material, for example through Generic Services projects such as:

- [Enrich Europeana](https://pro.europeana.eu/project/enrich-europeana)⁴ where partners showed strong interest in organising transcribathon events and provided access to the transcribathon platform, which proved engaging, and the project enabled work with the Europeana API, so that results go back into Europeana, although questions of software ownership were raised. Almost 20,000 annotations were provided.
- Crowd Heritage⁵ which developed an open platform⁶ where cultural heritage institutions can share their collections' metadata that need a fix or enrichment.
- Europeana-xx which will deliver User Generated Metadata (UGM), is organising a subtitle-a-thon and enabling user created galleries.

Some Generic Services (GS) projects e.g. initiatives with crowdsourcing components have posed new challenges for EF because they created new requirements of its main infrastructure and EDM, conceived chiefly as concerning validation and provenance.

The question of how to distinguish between 'official' (i.e. by a Europeana data provider/aggregator) submitted and external crowdsourced content remains an issue being considered by EF, alongside that of uneven quality in UGC. Clearer labelling and describing UGC is seen as one of a number of ways to address quality. Conversely the high-quality images needed for events such as transcribathons are frequently not available in Europeana content.

⁴ <https://pro.europeana.eu/project/enrich-europeana>

⁵ <https://pro.europeana.eu/project/crowd-heritage>

⁶ <https://crowdheritage.eu/en>

A bigger challenge related to the quality of crowdsourced contributions (especially metadata) is perceived around the open questions of is considered good / acceptable presentation quality and how this is validated. These concern the aggregators and CHIs, as well as EF, in terms of their potential role and responsibilities in a process which may be multi-step, complex and time-consuming.

Although the potential for mutual stimulation is recognised, EF is not currently positioned to deal with relationships with the many external Cultural Heritage crowdsourcing initiatives across Europe, whether the relatively widespread interactions between CHI and the GLAM-Wiki 'movement' or the numerous individual and heterogeneous projects and activities in Europe of the type outlined in this report, in view of the limitations on technical infrastructure and human capacity available within its current funding. Discussion within EF about how to leverage and make useful UGC in Europeana is ongoing and opinions diverse. Progress would require building new functionalities which sit together well with the current stack.

As things stand, the future roadmap is more likely to have a focus on User Generated Metadata (UGM) and handling enrichments to content accessible through Europeana, rather than UGC or storytelling. Standalone UGC submission forms are likely to remain available, but this currently stands outside the main Europeana aggregation system. For users familiarised with simple upload systems such as blogs or Facebook, the amount of time (often several weeks) required for content to be visible on Europeana, may well be a demotivating aspect.

It is an open question whether, within the Europeana ecosystem, there exists the potential to ease the barriers to discovery of and access to UGC, presented by the current heterogeneity of crowdsourcing initiatives across Europe, for example by using Europeana's influence and reputation to promote greater standardisation and interoperability in crowdsourcing by creating common guidelines, standards and methods for specific or analogous approaches within the wide crowdsourcing arena (at the same time perhaps increasing the potential for ingesting and presenting UGC through the Europeana pipeline, e.g. by addressing the relationship with EDM).

If so, a selective, segmented approach is likely to be necessary since each type of crowdsourcing activity has a different set of principles and challenges. On the one hand it could be difficult to provide anything very useful of an overarching nature; on the other, multiple guidelines, interviews and resources exist on ways to organise crowdsourcing events and other general topics.

In the continued pressure on resources to produce such guidelines at EF, the possibilities presented by future GS project calls and by the range of activities at disposal of the Europeana Network Association (Communities, Working Groups, Task Forces) are possible avenues for progress, alongside exploration of collaborations around the growing interest in Citizen Science for Cultural Heritage (e.g. supporting digital humanities research) analogous to progress in the natural sciences.

The process of engaging and involving new audiences has emerged as one of the main advantages of crowdsourcing activities, such as those linked to 'thon'-style events, collection days and tagging. The focus on people, communities, their stories and knowledge rather than objects per se, emphasises a new way of doing things.

One approach might be to enable users to edit metadata on Europeana Collections directly. The technical issues associated with this would need first to be addressed. However, it is unknown whether users might be motivated – or overwhelmed instead - by an invitation to create UGM on such a huge and diverse collection. Evidence suggests that they may, however, be more likely to become engaged in this way with local collections relevant to their lives or on topics with a thematic focus such as those identified by the Crowd Heritage initiative (e.g. on China and pagodas). A further line of argument is that, without visibility to the contributor, the motivation to create crowdsourced input may diminish. If so, this may again be more likely in local initiatives, perhaps especially events-based ones.

Arguably, crowd-enhanced metadata should be re-routed to any aggregator or CHI from which the content and original metadata was sourced. This raises the whole question of ‘roundtripping’, present also in contexts such as Wikidata, and how metadata generated centrally in Europeana Collections can benefit the content ‘owning’ institutions by allowing them, especially smaller ones, to do or build something they could not do alone. This would involve a number of considerations among different EF teams, such as where in EDM the metadata would sit.

2.2 National aggregators

Some, but not all, national aggregators are aware of a significant number of crowdsourcing initiatives in their country. About 74 such initiatives were identified by the survey respondents in total, of which several were Europeana-generated. A few national aggregators e.g. Ireland have been recently inspired to consider crowdsourcing opportunities, in their case through participation in Common Culture.

4 from 11 responding national aggregators have ingested content (4) or metadata (3) from crowdsourcing initiatives in their country, one of which was a Europeana initiative. However, the number of items ingested from these activities by responding national aggregators is small, exceeding 5000 in only one country (Finland). In the other three which have ingested it was under 1000 in total.

The main reason cited by national aggregators as standing in the way of ingesting crowdsourced material was not always being aware of them, followed closely by difficulties or uncertainties associated with technical issues, licensing, metadata or standards. Two aggregators cited their own policies towards UGC in general. No-one cited insufficient resources in their response, although the impression is that some national aggregators consider crowdsourcing as ‘a bridge too far’ and beyond their remit to aggregate from CHI, as well as their resources.

The types of content most prevalent in crowdsourcing activities of which national aggregators are aware are photographic images and text, although individual initiatives identified cover a range of other types including artworks/graphical creations, data, sound, video, social media posts and annotations. No 3D content was mentioned.

It appears that no more than around 1000 crowdsourced items have been ingested by Europeana from national aggregators responding to the survey. An amateur video platform for Dutch people to upload their own video footage from the 1960s, also at NISV (Netherlands) was mentioned as a possible future development.

Among the selection of external initiatives interviewed, Topothek (Austria) would like to get its content into Europeana and has discussed this several times with the Austrian aggregator, but digitisation (resolution) quality is a barrier, since their content is mainly generated through mobile technology and the ball remains in Topothek's court to filter out poor quality material. Ajapaik (Estonia) felt that local repositories are a higher priority for their country and that the aggregation of museums data to Europeana has been 'broken' for several years, so that data cannot be retrieved from Europeana, only from national museums portal. The recently redesigned Estonian national aggregation infrastructure does not consider UGC. Neither did DR, the Danish broadcaster, see the Danish national aggregator as currently equipped to handle their content. Meitheal Dúchas.ie (Ireland) have been in touch with DRI (the national aggregator) for advice about metadata but have no other relations with it and are doubtful whether DRI could handle the volume of transcriptions they generate: adding them to Europeana had been discussed but was shelved since it was uncertain how useful images of text would be. University College Dublin (UCD) is the content holder.

2.3 Thematic and domain aggregators

There were only two survey responses from Thematic and Domain aggregators. However, follow-up interviews arranged with several others revealed considerable interest emerging in crowdsourcing possibilities with a number of plans and initiatives described, alongside significant participation by some aggregators in DSI and GS projects.

A concern about sustainability and resourcing is evident among some thematic and domain aggregators e.g. in some cases those created in EU-funded projects have survived at a relatively low level of activity on a sporadic and largely voluntary basis. At least one is a 'dark aggregator' without independent web visibility. However, others, such as APE and Judaica are now reasonably well-established with a stable, if modest, number of staff: (APE has 3 FTE, Judaica 5).

Several thematic/domain aggregators see crowdsourcing as an important aspect of their future work and as the 'next layer in the content stack' and some have re-designed their infrastructure and tools (e.g. Judaica) in ways which enable the ingestion of crowdsourced content or for user transcription, annotation and adding complementary images or are in the process of doing so (e.g. APE). Judaica's contemporary aggregation system, with 'headless CMS', flexible API, open front end, new mappings and data standards, is seen as easy to open up to user contributions and crowdsourced content, in line with the prospect of being more than an aggregator but also an active platform and facilitator of projects and centrally-driven crowdsourcing initiatives, with aggregation as a core around which to build its position as an active player in the Jewish heritage domain. On the other hand, EU Screen – while recognising that UGC has a place and is important in supplementing knowledge of the past -does not currently submit crowdsourced audio-visual material or annotations to Europeana and is doubtful about the value of developing infrastructure for such a focus.

In some cases, providers of data to thematic/domain aggregators (e.g. Judaica) already include content from crowdsourcing campaigns. Others (e.g. APE), have identified issues which require further definition including:

- how does crowdsourced data relate to what comes from its data providers?
- how should the process work: centrally driven or in partnership with providers?
- could there be 'round-tripping' of crowdsourced metadata to local institutions?

Europeana Fashion conducts Community Engagement projects with schools and colleges involving curatorial activities and with Photoconsortium have recently commenced participation in the 3-year Citizen Heritage⁷ project funded under Erasmus+, which is investigating the integration of crowdsourcing and citizen participation in Cultural Heritage research, utilising the Crowd Heritage platform and seeking to provide Higher Education Institutions with new insights and opportunities to include Citizen Science activities for social purposes into their curricula, teaching and learning activities, and good practices in how to benefit from knowledge circulation in and outside academia and to adopt a more vibrant role in civil society. The Fifties in Europe Kaleidoscope project, which used the Crowd Heritage platform, validated the 8000 tags which were attached to Europeana content to allow a level of confidence: a next step is seen as being to analyse their 'scientific relevance'. Both these aggregators also participate in the Europeana-xx GS project.

Photoconsortium has concerned itself with the power of images as a way to share knowledge with communities not necessarily engaged with Cultural Heritage as illustrated by the Europeana China - Pagode⁸ project, identifying the point that, through popular photographic technology, a substantial part of Cultural Heritage is now initiated and maintained by the general public and represents an important potential tool for social sciences and digital humanities. Problems such as Tier 4 metadata quality, high resolution and using Artificial Intelligence (AI)/National Language Processing (NLP) are seen as addressable by taking a thematic perspective of this kind.

Europeana Sounds leveraged the huge footfall of Flickr by enhancing images of out of print books added to Europeana under the Europeana Creative project, with about 500,000 public tags which were used as subject terms and Europeana Radio⁹ made it possible to tag a piece of music from DBpedia, although the location of these is now unknown: it sees scope for further development of the idea by a more controlled approach to genre and other description. The possibility of transcribing sheet music on Europeana as an audio file (midi player) is another possibility under exploration, where specialised knowledge is needed, and content would need to be stored in the Cloud or on an external server.

Some support was voiced for the concept of increasing direct crowdsourcing interaction on Europeana Collections itself: where tags can be added, or errors corrected by individuals, CHI or aggregators, thereby increasing engagement. The benefits of greater control and easier 'round-tripping' to CHI and aggregators may outweigh the extra work needed. However, quite close monitoring and safeguards were identified as needs, e.g. validated email addresses.

2.4 External initiatives

Survey responses were received from 19 countries, with 3 from Greece being the highest number. Additional pointers to wider crowdsourcing networks in other countries, including 5 other EU member states, were received from the Wikimedia Sweden chapter.

The **heterogeneity** of the crowdsourcing was evident in the sheer variety of goals, approaches and infrastructures in these responses and amplified even in the relatively small sample of projects selected

⁷ <https://www.citizenheritage.eu/>

⁸ <https://pro.europeana.eu/project/pagode-europeana-china>

⁹ <http://radio-player.europeana.eu/>

for follow-up interviews. Further information of the initiatives included in the sample can be found in Annexes 3 and 4. The interviewed sample included:

- Topothek (Austria) a decentralised NGO-driven infrastructure system in which contributors do the digitisation. Its objective is to get private collections into public hands and by doing so to put people in touch with historic sources, providing new insights ('remembrance' rather than history). Topotheks collect content and make it accessible, others are invited to interpret. Their 'matrix' is both scientific and public for citizen science, seen as a close-to-the-ground and approachable entrance for citizens, while a 'top-down' access point such as Europeana remains important does not yet have a central website, local Topothek instances are separately searched. Projects to enable cross-searching currently under testing and the first mobile version may be available in January 2021.
- Ajapaik (Estonia) is ten year old NGO initiative specialising in 'rephotography' or repeat photography: a 'then and now' approach involving, contemporary photos of a historic view.
- Monument Monitor (UK) is a two-month-old, one-person PhD project, jointly sponsored by University College London and Historic Environment Scotland (HES). It involves 20 mainly small and rural heritage case study sites across the Highlands and islands of Scotland in testing how visitor photos be used for reliable conservation data.
- Herbarium (Portugal) began because they felt a crowdsourcing platform would help increase the pace of digitisation of the herbarium collection.
- DR (Denmark). Through an, initially internal, repository of this broadcasting organisation, researchers provide archive clips to radio/TV journalists. It was made available to the public 6 or 7 years ago by putting radio clips into a phone and asking the public for keywords and through a competitive game for tagging TV clips. Funding was then obtained for digitising photo archives, starting with the oldest pictures in the repository which had little or no metadata.
- Meitheal Dúchas.ie (Ireland) is the national Folklore collection a relatively simple but very successful collaboration between two universities to scan and index several million pages collected in 1937-39 by school children, who were sent home to collect stories which their teachers transcribed simply in copy books beside a page of text in children's best handwriting. It has grown more or less of its own accord and is a highly popular. Folkloric topics collected include (non-exhaustively) local stories, history, famine monuments, toys, food, 'games I like to play' poems and prayers.
- Heritage Quest (Netherlands). Initiated by a Dutch university, with a large archaeology department, in 2018, this project leverages the national LIDAR infrastructure to raise public interest in archaeological heritage, by identifying burial mounds and other sites in forests, then putting the data on Zooniverse. It now works on three different projects involving university and local public regional partnerships. The scientific component is important for the universities.

Geographical scope

From 27 projects/initiatives responding to the survey, 15 designated their scope as having a national dimension, 10 a European dimension and 4 had international scope (all either singly or jointly). 11 had regional/local scope but only two of these solely so.

Funding, human resources and sustainability

The majority (18) of projects responding to the survey had national funding. 9 were funded at regional/local level e.g. by municipalities, 6 were EU-funded, 6 by NGOs or Foundations and 6 generated their own income, while 2 were privately subsidised. 10 of the responding initiatives are ongoing, without fixed duration, whereas 6 did not know owing to uncertain funding or other factors. 8 had been underway for 3 years or less.

From the interviews:

Local *Topotheks* (Austria) are mainly run and funded by municipalities (or sometimes their archives) but also associations.

Ajapaik (Estonia) is an ongoing initiative, without end date, but underfunding is its trickiest issue. Crowdfunding from Estonian sources has raised 92,00 Euros over several years, together with some Finnish funding. *Ajapaik* has one member of core staff supplemented by voluntary crowdsourcing.

The budget of *Monument Monitor* (UK) was removed because of COVID and submission numbers have significantly decreased during Lockdown.

For *Herbarium* (Portugal). Staff continuity in general is a current problem. Sustainability depends on compacts with or funding from foundations, schools, but is at present difficult.

The *DR* platform (Denmark) is open access, but photos cannot be downloaded (except by DR journalists because they are still sold commercially). It is not yet clear yet whether their strategy will be to share this more widely – but an interesting issue, since it will be ‘homeless’ in a year or so. The Cultural Heritage site is now outdated, and they are in a transitional state and could be interested to consider whether Europeana or a thematic/domain aggregator could be a home (there is already some DR content on Europeana). The service currently pays for itself, but there is a lack of budget for rectifying any problems.

Meitheal Dúchas.ie (Ireland) would be interested to explore any value in its corpus being more widely available alongside similar material, which could be interesting for folklorists. It has sufficient public funding is sufficient and four FTE staff. Bids for funding are required every 3 years to the government department responsible for the Irish language. which is a priority. Cross translations Irish-English are also under consideration. Failing this, University College Dublin (UCD) would keep preservation copies and an access site would require a new plan.

Heritage Quest (Netherlands). Its work is funded by provinces (who are obliged to care for Cultural Heritage under Dutch law) and also has funding from provincial innovation budgets. There is a continuous quest for funding. Scientists also contribute their free time. However, although the

Netherlands occupies a relatively small area, they do not have the manpower to take on enormous task and have turned to crowdsourcing.

Aims, activities and tasks

A large majority of the crowdsourcing initiatives (24/27) cited community engagement and participation as among their major aims. After this came preservation/documentation (18) and knowledge discovery and management (13).

The activity carried out most frequently by responding initiatives was collecting digitised objects or data (18/27), followed by quality enhancement, transcription, and processing/analysing/interpreting information or datasets (10). Only 9 carried out preparation of data/metadata for aggregation elsewhere. No initiatives supported the collective building of digital artefacts such as 3D models.

A wide range of tasks were crowdsourced, the most frequent being digitising/uploading (14/27), categorising (11), tagging/annotation (10) and linking (7). 18/27 responding initiatives collected photographs, followed by archival or text-based documents (14), then sound, video, online metadata and cultural artifacts (each with 8).

Among the respondents Archives were the most frequent type of facilitating/coordinating body (10/27), followed by research institutions (9), higher education institutions (8), libraries (7), and NGOs (6). However, the range of types of organisation was wide.

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18/27 responding initiatives collected photographs, followed by archival or text-based documents (14), then sound, video, online metadata and cultural artifacts (each with 8). It is usual to organise different kinds of supporting events and activities in conjunction with crowdsourcing activities, including 'thons' (hackathon, transcribathon, editathon), publicity, contests and workshops, among others.

Technical platform/infrastructure/submission process

There was no apparent favoured option among potential crowdsourcing platforms and a wide variety of options was deployed (including self-built or none). The most usual mode of collection was web-based (20/27) but collection by mobile, by social media and in analogue form were also common. Content storage methods cited were a relatively even mix of internal repositories (13) and cloud-based systems (10).

From the interview sample:

Monument Monitor. A former software engineer, the project manager built the platform herself and is open to its more robust development, if her post-doctoral application is successful. HES may bring the project in-house. Site visitors Tweet, Instagram, email or WhatsApp to send images in and their usefulness is assessed for data aggregation. WhatsApp and email are seen as the best ways of sending photos (rather than Twitter or Instagram): it is easy to take and convenient just to send lots of photos on WhatsApp and email does not compress them.

Herbarium. The Herbarium platform is integrated in the digitisation workflow of University of Coimbra, as a side project of their main work, developing an integration with their CMS, reducing human intervention, using what was good in other platforms and adding features. They take pictures of their specimens and the crowd transcribes. Contributors are invited to complete information about specimens in batches of images, organised in projects (e.g. 'grasses of Guinea-Bissau'). There are several defined levels of difficulty depending on contributor experience and number of validated submissions. All validation is automated with points allocated according to experience (for example. 6 beginners x 10 points or an expert with 60 amounts to the same level of validation). The challenge set is for users to improve their ranking.

DR A competent in-house programmer and an existing platform with API between major Danish initiatives were building blocks. The site is simple, not all tags are correct, but it is not possible to remove previous tags. All tags have now been moved into a general internal site for photos and tags which it is hoped (but not certain) to maintain for general use. Storage is in the cloud.

Meitheal Dúchas.ie uses its own platform and is hoping to continue. A photo collection is also to be opened on the site for crowdsourced tagging, alongside transcription for longer stories in Irish. It was decided not to use OCR because people enjoyed transcribing so much. The standard of transcription is very high. community engagement a major aim. Some super-users have transcribed thousands of pages

Heritage Quest. People tag everything they notice on Zooniverse by click location on the screen the location where they see it. every map is investigated by 15-16 people. Following that, scientist and archaeologists go with the volunteers into the field. However, COVID has slowed down field work. An entire region is divided into small images of 300m x 300m (the best scale for archaeology) and the threshold raised to 30 people. The map s retired, exported to GIS, cleaned up and filtered. A PhD is working on machine learning to detect burial mounds.

Collections

Among the respondents, archives were the most frequent type of facilitating coordinating body (10/27), followed by research institutions 9, higher education institutions (8), libraries (7), and NGOs (6). However, the range of types of organisation was wide.

The size of many crowdsourced collections is relatively small, but some of those responding has grown substantial. In total, the responding initiatives approach almost 3 million metadata records, 2 million digital objects and exceed 2 million user interventions (tags, annotations etc). The mean average metadata records per initiative appears to be over 100,000, the median about 7500.

Among the projects interviewed, the *Ajapaik* collection is quite large at 200,000 items with content mainly in Estonian but some also Finnish. It also includes pictorial forms such as Graphic art and moving images. At *DR* (Denmark). 138,000 photos have been digitised and metadata crowdsourced to assist discovery. 340,000 tags have been contributed in the last 3 or 4 years. At *Meitheal Dúchas.ie* (Ireland) to date, 300,000 pages have been transcribed by a very wide range of people (283,000 in English, 46,000 in Irish): far more than expected.

Contributors

A wide cross-section of the population has participated in crowdsourcing activities of different kinds, covering most age groups.

15 of the survey respondents had more than 500 contributing participants, 6 having more than 2000. 5 respondents had less 50. The range of motivations for participation was wide with a balance, at the most general level, between learning and the desire to contribute to or promote something.

From the Interview sample:

Monument Monitor. The demographic of people submitting has even age splits up to the over 70s. There are about 4.5 photos per submission and 1500 participants to date.

Herbarium. Launching in April 2020, contributors started with 200 students at the University, after which the initiative was promoted by Internet and Social Media and to high school students and retired people. Users create accounts and contribute for varying durations. A need is felt for greater interaction with contributors and the platform is being developed for that. A continuous stream is important, and lack of interaction may lead to people ceasing to contribute: a need is felt to increase dissemination and engage more people.

DR. Google Analytics shows more than 2000 contributors: some of the major ones are retired personnel from DR who have precise knowledge. Crowdsourced tags were made immediately searchable, helping create contributor excitement.

Meitheal Dúchas.ie Almost everyone can find a relative who is interested in participating. The service is very popular in education. However, GDPR makes it difficult to contact them.

Heritage Quest. Volunteers are currently being trained to do inspections in the fields (to identify which 'hills' are burial mounds and which natural) Under Dutch law, only registered archaeologists can do actual quarrying, but volunteers may help with administration. The field work is an enormous task.

Data models, metadata and protocols

23/27 responding initiatives created metadata manually, but in 14 of these cases in conjunction with metadata captured from external sources and/or automatically-generated. One respondent described its metadata as auto-generated only. The metadata and identifier standards in use by respondents remain heterogeneous. Dublin Core is still the most frequently used metadata standard (6/27), 5 used home-grown schemes and 6 none at all. 10 used DOI or other persistent identifiers, one each used EDM and IIF. 9/27 respondents did not use a recognised exchange protocol, a few referred to XML/RDF in various contexts and 5 used OAI PMH.

From the interviews:

Topothek (Austria) already uses DC for tags/comments and OAI PMH. Vocabulary control to assist consistent user annotations is an area where support is seen as needed.

In *Ajapaik* (Estonia), content is enriched with added metadata. Until 2019, its crowdsourced activities were mainly geotagging but since last year, several other micro tasks have been added, such as face

tagging. It has its own data model for their very specific data and an Open Data API, but no repository is currently taking their data back. IIF is currently being implemented and the live server moved to an image server. Metadata tends to be messy (without causing big problems), but they plan to be more standardised and mappings are in place. It was using ESE but now plans to import from LIDO. They are not very familiar with EDM. Social validation of metadata works but can be improved: the idea is to have a low participation barrier: no moderation is performed but trustworthiness of users is calculated based on contributions.

At *Meitheal Dúchas.ie* .crowdsourced metadata is not involved: they index and create metadata themselves and decided not to do community tagging.

Quality

Most responding initiatives carried out validation of user contributions. Other types of evaluation listed were all used but markedly less prevalent in each case.

The development and application of quality criteria in an environment of huge quantities of crowd-generated content are at the heart of future developments. Both technical quality and content relevance are identified issues. The perceived difficulty of predicting relevance in an environment where contribution is open to anyone may be seen as a contrast to the task of CHI as knowledge keepers - and to potentially 'elitist' views. However: big questions are raised such as: how to determine what is interesting and relevant and whether a 'hybrid' approach (citizen-sourced but expert validated) is feasible?

This applies, not least, to the vast amount of UGC stored in social media, requiring ever-increasing data storage in the cloud, raising issues about its sustainability, how its curation would work (and whether a, which of it is worth keeping, who should decide: the end user or whether a CHI-based selection model remains appropriate?

Within the interview sample:

Topothek. Quality assurance is maintained by regular contact with local Topotheks.

Monument Monitor. The main data emerging is on the number of visitors, which is not really useful for conservation. Discussions are in process with conservationists to try to decide what visitor instructions should be provided. This methodology does not seem ultra-useful for creating 3D models as is suggested by the literature, since asking visitors to take photos to be taken all round the monument (compared with photogrammetry or laser scanning) provides a 'gappy' result of insufficient quality for creating 3D models.

Impact Assessment

Only 4 initiatives said they carried out impact assessment.

From those interviewed, *Herbarium* before launch asked high school students to do pre-test on knowledge, then 2 hours later a post-test. They have a social science/biologist collaborator for future IAs post-COVID and are seeking more innovative means of Impact Assessment than questionnaires – e.g. through expressive representations.

Licensing

Creative Commons licences are in wide use, but 9/27 respondents do not use any licensing. From the interviewees: at *DR* rights issues would need to be considered in considering any transfer of holdings.

Wider aggregation ecosystems

Two of the interview sample threw light on the way aggregation works in content disciplines which neighbour or overlap Cultural Heritage.

Herbarium. Several generic platforms exist to digitise herbarium specimens, e.g. Zooniverse, Living Atlases (Australia, modified in Belgium) which work in a similar way. There are a number of global biodiversity information aggregators: Herbarium exports its data to GBIF, run by a consortium of governments. They are in touch with other platform owners, including a COST action to mobilise data in collections, other crowdsourcing platforms for natural sciences and developers of their CMS software in order to improve the information flow between platforms.

Heritage Quest. Regarding data aggregation, it is not yet at that stage. Work is proceeding on an App in which all information is stored. The wish is to be transparent for volunteers but otherwise archaeology is protected in the Netherlands, so the database will not be published on the Internet. Heritage agencies will all have access, including in other European countries, when the time comes. Leiden university has a project website, currently only in Dutch but in English from January 2021. As a next step they will hand the results over to Rijksdienst.

Citizen Science

Citizen Science was the most frequently cited context for a crowdsourcing project (17/27), followed by storytelling (8) and Wikidata (5). In all this, the 'fence' exist between scientific and popular communities can be relatively high, although public interest in science has increased. Low threshold metadata systems are seen as needed to support citizen science, with the right, simple structures and requirements such as Dublin Core and gamification. .

From the interviews:

Monument Monitor sees its project as much more Citizen Science than crowdsourcing: being about trying to find reliable data for heritage scientists.

Heritage Quest identifies as a Citizen Science project covering archaeology. Netherlands is covered by publicly available LIDAR providing detailed data from altitude for 3D models. This is almost impossible through conventional techniques because of vegetation. It is now possible to see the ground surface in forests for the first time, including: burial mounds, Celtic fields, prehistoric archaeological sites etc.

GLAM-WIKI

Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons, Wikidata, and Wikisource are particularly relevant to digital heritage. Wikidata is a collaboratively edited database of structured information to which more than a billion statements have been added. Wikidata provides a general framework for bridging the metadata, vocabularies, and languages used by CHI to describe their collections, opening up possibilities for discovery and connection across repositories and weaving institutional knowledge into the semantic web. Through the community's efforts, there is now a growing corpus of more than a quarter million

paintings on Wikidata, with a normalized metadata model, and corresponding images on Wikimedia Commons. Wikimedians collaborate with galleries, libraries, archives, museums and other knowledge and memory-holding institutions united by the common goal of preserving cultural heritage and sharing knowledge with the world. There have been hundreds of partnerships around the world. The response from Wikimedia Sverige to the external initiatives survey in Annex 3 provides an overview of some of these activities in Europe.

Europeana Sounds has been involved in a number of events ('thons') wikidata. In this case, different file formats for embedded sound between Wikipedia and Europeana are an identified constraint. Links to data providers on Europeana, backed by web analytics, could create extra value for them, plus incentives to share and reduce any fear of losing traffic.

Among external initiatives Ajapaik sees increasing traction in the GLAM-Wiki domain and want to create more connections e.g. by publish all rephotographs under CC for export to Wikimedia Commons next to historic pictures and have a developing relationship with wikidata with goals of knowledge accessibility perceived as similar and therefore collaboration as natural. However, Wikimedia commons is very strict on copyright and the copyright status on much of what they publish is not yet clear.

3 Conclusions and proposals

The Interim Report (October 2020) identified a number of areas for further investigation and possible recommendations during the remainder of the study, including:

1. Does crowdsourced DCH currently hold added value and sufficient quality to justify effort to increase its aggregation within the Europeana ecosystem and ingestion by Europeana?
2. How are the crowdsourcing campaigns generated centrally by Europeana to date, positioned in the whole European 'universe' of crowdsourcing?
3. How can Europeana benefit by increased community engagement and audience participation through DCH crowdsourcing?
4. Could Europeana and its ecosystem of aggregators and CHI play a stronger role in promoting, encouraging, coordinating widespread DCH crowdsourcing projects which support its objectives?
5. Can Europeana lead by helping standardise methods, standards and infrastructure in this widely heterogeneous field so as to promote sustainability and interoperability?
6. What is the scope for further cooperation with important 'neighbouring' crowdsourcing 'movements' such as Wikimedia and Citizen Science?

Conclusions

Knowledge production today relies increasingly on exchanges between groups of people who connect through the Internet. The emergence of online public spaces from an interactive and interconnected World Wide Web has enabled new practices of data and information generation, sharing and aggregation, which can happen in many forms. Collaborative data collection is enabled by bespoke websites built for specific institutions or groups, created to involve interested volunteers in the digitisation of collections that support multiple agendas.

Over the decade or more since the first Cultural Heritage crowdsourcing initiatives were launched, there has been a significant proliferation of initiatives. Those identified by this study (see Annex 4) are likely to constitute a relatively small proportion of those which have taken place. Transience and low visibility of some activities, especially local ones, is a significant feature in this field.

In Cultural Heritage, at the 'top end' The British Library has in recent years set up the LibCrowds¹⁰ platform for hosting experimental crowdsourcing projects aimed at improving access to the diverse collections they hold, while GlobalXplorer¹¹ enables the inspection of satellite images to help understand the current state of preservation of archaeology-rich landscapes worldwide. Even the relatively modest number of responses to the survey of External Initiatives in this research accounts for several millions of crowdsourced digital objects, metadata records and user enhancements (tags, annotations, transcriptions etc.). It is highly probable that this only scratches the surface. The vast amount of User Generated Content held in the international Social Media presents a further issue, currently seen as too big and difficult to contemplate action.

Perceptions of low value and of a 'wall' between crowdsourced digital material and that collected by Cultural Heritage Institutions have also diminished considerably, with a stronger sense and evidence emerging that crowdsourced content not only has complementary value in helping understand our culture and history, but also provides a powerful means of engaging communities and the public's participation in their cultural heritage.

Europeana has also played an important role in stimulating crowdsourcing through its several centrally-driven campaigns on various topics. Several Generic Services projects have also made useful contributions to various aspects.

Nevertheless, the field remains extremely heterogeneous and in the main, it is also necessary for the user to visit the website of each individual initiative to use its results. The extent of aggregation of content from similar initiatives remains very limited and compares unfavourably with other disciplines where there is a high level of crowdsourcing activity such as natural sciences and biodiversity. Preservation and archiving are also uneven because resource-driven. This is an increasingly serious problem, since it is likely to have already led to the disappearance or irretrievability of a large amount of valuable digital cultural heritage content.

National aggregators in the Europeana ecosystem have, until now, mainly seen UGC as something outside their main scope or beyond their resources, although this may now be beginning to change. Several thematic and domain aggregators have undertaken a patchwork of activities, recognise a need to act and are planning accordingly. At the Europeana Foundation, there is awareness and much discussion of the issues at stake, but the limitations upon the available capacity of technical resources create a difficulty in prioritising what would undoubtedly be a substantial task.

¹⁰ <https://www.libcrowds.com/>

¹¹ <https://www.globalxplorer.org/>

Proposals

1. **Aggregation**. The first question, then, is whether it is possible to create an aggregation 'pipeline' system for User Generated Content, on similar principles to those adopted with success to those used by Europeana in aggregating diverse digital content from CHI. In thinking about this, it could be useful to look in depth at what has been done in other fields, such as natural science/biodiversity and in Citizen Science more generally, how far this has succeeded, whether it could be emulated in cultural heritage and who could lead such an initiative. A current fulcrum would clearly be how the Europeana Data Model (EDM) could be modified and enhanced for greater hospitability to metadata of crowdsourced content and what mappings would be needed.
2. **Guidance and standardisation**. Guidance on a more consistent and standardised approach to crowdsourcing between external initiatives could be effective in increasing common practices, technical interoperability and thereby aggregation, increased access and re-use. Furthermore, whether Europeana's reputation in the field of digital culture could add strength to any such guidance.
3. **Segmenting guidance**. Given the heterogeneity of aims, approaches and most other aspects of crowdsourcing initiatives, it would almost certainly be necessary to divide any such guidance according to different types of crowdsourcing, since an attempt to create overarching guidelines would likely result in superficial generalisation and limited utility in practice (and there are, for instance, many available sources on how to organise crowdsourcing events and different types of 'thons') Such a segmentation would need to cover User Generated Content, User Metadata Enhancements, Transcription and other main categories of crowdsourcing.
4. **Resourcing the work**. Since the production of guidance might well create a strain on the already stretched human resources at EF, the possibility of engaging expertise from within the membership of the Europeana Network Association in a Task Force or other form could be considered. Likewise, a new Generic Services project could address the whole question of an aggregation infrastructure for crowdsourcing.
5. **3D modelling**. The tantalising possibility of crowdsourcing data acquisition in support of 3D modelling of Cultural Heritage has been partially realised in several initiatives, but much work remains to develop a consistently adoptable approach. This suggests a possible need for a separate project on this topic.
6. **Quality**. Behind everything lie remaining uncertainties about how to assess the quality and value of crowdsourced content and data and how to consider it in the context of what Cultural Heritage Institutions collect. The notion of quality has a number of aspects including technical quality (resolution etc.), accuracy of metadata inputs, contextual relevance etc. It is as yet unresolved. Initiatives such as the 'gold, silver, bronze' approach recently launched by Crowd Heritage are certainly worth taking into account.

Annex 1 – Survey of National Aggregators

Respondents

Country	Organisation	Name of national aggregator
1 Austria	uma information technology gmbh	Kulturpool
2 Bulgaria	"Pencho Slaveykov" Regional Library	Public Library - Varna
3 Finland	National Library of Finland / Finna	Formula Aggregation Service of the National Library of Finland
4 Greece	National Documentation Centre	searchculture.gr
5 Hungary		Hungarian National Museum / MuseuMap
6 Ireland	Digital Repository of Ireland	Digital Repository of Ireland
7 Netherlands	Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision	Digitale Collectie
8 Poland	PSNC	Federacja Bibliotek Cyfrowych (FBC)
9 Serbia	National Library of Serbia	Aggregator for Europeana
10 Slovenia	National and University Library	Slovenian National E-content Aggregator
11 Sweden	Swedish National Heritage Board	SOCH

Table 1: List of respondents for Survey 1

1.1 How many DCH crowdsourcing initiatives are you aware of in your country (including those organised internationally or by Europeana)?

Overview

Figure 1: Awareness of DCH crowdsourcing initiatives

Survey responses

Organisation	Current/ongoing	Completed 2017-20	Completed before 2017	None
1 uma information technology gmbh	3	1	0	1
2 "Pencho Slaveykov" Regional Library				1
3 National Library of Finland / Finna	9	16	1	
4 National Documentation Centre	2	0	1	
5 Hungary	10			
6 Digital Repository of Ireland	5	4	2	
7 Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision	4	4		
8 PSNC	0	3	0	
9 National Library of Serbia	0	1	1	
10 National and University Library (Slovenia)	0	0	0	1
11 Swedish National Heritage Board	6	1		

Table 2: Awareness of DCH crowdsourcing initiatives

Additional comments

Organisation	Please add a URL and/or contact details for any these
2 "Pencho Slaveykov" Regional Library	
3 National Library of Finland / Finna	<p>Several projects of Wikimedia Finland in co-operation with Finnish CHIs (contacts susanna.anas@gmail.com, kimmo.virtanen@gmail.com) - some examples: Wiki Loves Monuments http://wlm.wikimedia.fi/en/tervetuloa-english/; Helsinki Rephotography https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Helsinki_rephotography; Wikidocumentaries https://blog.wikidocumentaries.io/en/. See also: crowdsourcing initiative in co-operation with wikidata and Wikimedia Finland for collecting industrial history of Tampere for a new museum http://www.werstas.fi/tule-werstaalle/tietoa-werstaasta/nykyiset-hankkeet/ (contact info@tyovaenmuseo.fi) ; public calls to suggest materials related to COVID-19 for web archiving https://www.kansalliskirjasto.fi/fi/uutiset/koronakesanmuistot-talteen and https://www.kansalliskirjasto.fi/fi/uutiset/kansalliskirjasto-keraa-verkkosisaltoja-koronavapusta-ja-arjesta-verkkoarkistoon (contact aija.vahtola@helsinki.fi); Nordic project Collecting Social Photo https://www.valokuvataiteenmuseo.fi/en/projects/collecting-</p>

		<p>social-photo; Finnish topotheques https://www.topothek.at/en/ (contact in Finland tomi.ahoranta@arkisto.fi); Albumit auki (sharing photos from family albums) https://albumitauki.fi/; Co-Creation of Cultural Heritage Databank of Rauma city (contact minna-liisa.salonsaari@rauma.fi); Project Fredrika (Wikipedia project with some Finnish CHIs) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Projekt_Fredrika; crowdsourcing initiative for collecting aviation history https://ilmailumuseo.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/2020_loppuraportti_Evergreens_pi-enennetty.pdf (contact tapio.juutinen@ilmailumuseo.fi); crowdsourcing initiative for collecting industrial history of Varkaus city https://www.varkaus.fi/teollisuuden-tekijat-toiminta (contact tytti.harkonen@varkaus.fi); crowdsourcing initiative for heritage related to eating and drinking https://suomisyojajuo.fi/ (contact hrm@hotelljaravintolamuseo.fi).</p>
4	National Documentation Centre	https://www.istorima.org/ , https://hermoupolis.omeka.net/
6	Digital Repository of Ireland	<p>https://www.dri.ie/europeana-sport-ireland, https://www.huntmuseum.com/2020/05/01/ardnacrusha-memories-collecting-your-stories-about-the-shannon-hydro-electric-scheme/, https://www.tcd.ie/library/lockdown-living/, Digital Repository of Ireland is also preparing a COVID-19 related crowdsourcing campaign, Dublin City Library and Archives is planning a metadata enrichment event, http://letters1916.maynoothuniversity.ie/, https://repository.dri.ie/catalog/1c18df827, https://pro.europeana.eu/event/europeana-migration-collection-day-new-irish-communities, an upcoming project on Archiving The 8th run by DRI will also involve crowdsourcing</p>
7	Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision	<p>https://velehanden.nl/ ; https://www.nederlandsfotomuseum.nl/captions-for-cas/ ; https://www.euroclio.eu/crowd-sourcing/ ; https://crowdheritage.eu/en</p>
8	PSNC	<p>Transcribathon Wroclaw https://www.facebook.com/events/2701447519976756/, Transcribathon Warszawa https://transcribathon.com/en/runs/poland/, Zbiorki FBC https://fbc.pionier.net.pl/zbiorki/dlibra?action=ChangeLanguageAction&language=pl</p>
9	National Library of Serbia	<p>https://www.nb.rs/events/event.php?id=33889 (2018), https://euinfo.rs/srbija-u-europeani-mobilizacija-secanja-na-prvi-svetski-rat/ (2014) - both in Serbian and both events organized in cooperation with Europeana</p>

1.2. Have the results of any of these initiatives been ingested by the national aggregator? (Content and Metadata)

Overview

Figure 2: Numbers ingested into national aggregator

Survey responses

Organisation	Content		Metadata		Not answered
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
1 uma information technology gmbh					
2 "Pencho Slaveykov" Regional Library					
3 National Library of Finland / Finna					
4 National Documentation Centre					
5 Hungary					
6 Digital Repository of Ireland					
7 Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision					
8 PSNC					
9 National Library of Serbia					
10 National and University Library					
11 Swedish National Heritage Board					

Table 3: Numbers ingested into national aggregator

Additional comments

Organisation	Please provide the names of these initiatives
1 uma information technology gmbh	https://www.topothek.at/en/what-is-the-topotheque/ , https://www.onb.ac.at/ueber-uns/presse/pressemeldungen/oesterreich-aus-der-luft-oesterreichische-nationalbibliothek-startet-erste-crowdsourcing-kampagne , https://www.geschichtewiki.wien.gv.at/Wien_Geschichte_Wiki
3 National Library of Finland / Finna	At least the results of Albumit auki -initiative. We might have ingested some more as parts of CHIs datasets.
4 National Documentation Centre	Istorima, HERMOUPOLIS DIGITAL HERITAGE MANAGEMENT (HERMES)
6 Digital Repository of Ireland	Letters of 1916, Inspiring Ireland Public Memorabilia. Others planned for the future include COVID-19 community response, Dublin City Library & Archives, Archiving the 8th.
8 PSNC	Transcribathon Wroclaw, Transcribathon Warszawa, Zbiorki FBC
9 National Library of Serbia	Europeana Migration Collection Day, Belgrade 19-20 October 2018
10 National and University Library (Slovenia)	
11 Swedish National Heritage Board	The Unstraight Museum

1.3. How many items from these crowdsourcing initiatives are currently held by your national aggregation repository?

Overview

Figure 3: Number of crowdsourcing items held in national aggregation repository

Survey responses

Organisation	None	<100	100-500	500-1000	1000-5000	>5000	Not answered
1 uma information technology gmbh							
2 "Pencho Slaveykov" Regional Library							
3 National Library of Finland / Finna							
4 National Documentation Centre							
5 Hungary							
6 Digital Repository of Ireland							
7 Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision							
8 PSNC							
9 National Library of Serbia							
10 National and University Library (Slovenia)							
11 Swedish National Heritage Board							

Table 4: Number of crowdsourcing items held in national aggregation repository

1.4. How many items from these crowdsourcing initiatives have been ingested from you by Europeana?

Survey responses

Organisation	Number of items
1 uma information technology gmbh	0
2 "Pencho Slaveykov" Regional Library	
3 National Library of Finland / Finna	0
4 National Documentation Centre	0
5 Hungary	
6 Digital Repository of Ireland	74
7 Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision	
8 PSNC	1000
9 National Library of Serbia	17
10 National and University Library (Slovenia)	
11 Swedish National Heritage Board	

Table 5: Number of crowdsourcing initiatives ingested by Europeana

1.5. What are the main types of content involved?

Overview

Figure 4: Types on content

Survey responses

Organisation	Photographic images	Artworks or graphical	Text	Data	Sound	Video	3D	Social media posts	Other
1 uma information technology gmbh									
2 "Pencho Slaveykov" Regional Library									
3 National Library of Finland / Finna									
4 National Documentation Centre									
5 Hungary									
6 Digital Repository of Ireland									
7 Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision									
8 PSNC									
9 National Library of Serbia									
10 National and University Library (Slovenia)									
11 Swedish National Heritage Board									

Table 6: Types of content

Question responses to 'Other' option

Organisation	Other
7 Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision	Annotations

1.6. What factors (if any) stand in the way of ingesting from crowdsourcing activities?

Overview

Figure 5: Factors affecting ingestion from crowdsourcing activities

Survey responses

Organisation	We are not always aware of them	Our policies/ strategies do not include them	There is not enough time or resource to include them in our portfolio	Difficulties/uncertainties associated with technical issues, licensing, metadata or standards	Other
1 uma information technology gmbh					
2 "Pencho Slaveykov" Regional Library					
3 National Library of Finland / Finna					
4 National Documentation Centre					
5 Hungary					
6 Digital Repository of Ireland					

7	Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision				
8	PSNC				
9	National Library of Serbia				
10	National and University Library				
11	Swedish National Heritage Board				

Table 7: Factors affecting ingestion from crowdsourcing activities

Question responses to 'Other' option

Organisation	Other
6. Digital Repository of Ireland	Organisations with their own websites are sometimes reluctant to deposit content and metadata in a repository as they don't want to lose traffic, it's an ongoing discussion that we are having with them :).

Additional comments

Organisation	Please add any other relevant information
4 National Documentation Centre	We have a policy to work with institutions and not directly with users. For the above mentioned projects there is an institution that mediates to guarantee the quality of the content. In the case of hermoupolis the documentation standards followed are not compatible with our standards
5 Hungary	Not sure about the "before 2017" questions though - I just started working in a CHI around 2 years ago.
6. Digital Repository of Ireland	We have a lot of plans for future crowdsourcing events

1.7. Would you be willing to participate in a short follow-up interview about this subject?

Organisation	Yes	No
1 uma information technology gmbh		
2 "Pencho Slaveykov" Regional Library (Bulgaria)		
3 National Library of Finland / Finna		
4 National Documentation Centre (Greece)		
5 Hungary		
6 Digital Repository of Ireland		
7 Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision		
8 PSNC (Poland)		
9 National Library of Serbia		
10 National and University Library (Slovenia)		
11 Swedish National Heritage Board		

Overview

Figure 6: Future survey participation

Annex 2 – Survey of Thematic and domain aggregators

Respondents

Country	Organisation	Name of national aggregator
1 Archaelology	CARARE	CARARE
2 Italy	Photoconsortium	Photoconsortium

Table 8: List of respondents for Survey 2

2.1. How many DCH crowdsourcing initiatives are you aware of in your domain/thematic area (including those organised internationally or by Europeana)?

Survey responses

Organisation	Current/ongoing	Completed 2017-20	Completed before 2017	None
1 CARARE	2	0	0	
2 Photoconsortium		4	3	

Table 9: Awareness of DCH crowdsourcing initiatives

Additional comments

Organisation	Please add a URL and/or contact details for any these
2 CARARE	It is not clear how crowdsourcing is defined, or how you propose to use this information, so if you would like further details please email me.
3 Photoconsortium	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Europeana_1914-1918 ; https://pro.europeana.eu/project/europeana-1989 ; https://pro.europeana.eu/page/europeana-migration ; https://pro.europeana.eu/project/crowd-heritage ; https://pro.europeana.eu/post/rediscover-the-1950s-presenting-the-fifties-in-europe-kaleidoscope-project ; https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/article/all-our-yesterdays-a-huge-success-for-the-photographic-exhibition/ ; https://www.photoconsortium.net/arno-compagno-di-vita/

2.2 Have the results of any of these initiatives been ingested by your domain/thematic aggregator?

Survey responses

Organisation	Content		Metadata		Not answered
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
1 CARARE					
2 Photoconsortium					

Table 10: Numbers ingested into national aggregator

Additional comments

Organisation	Please provide the names of these initiatives
1 CARARE	PAN data will be aggregated by CARARE, so the answer is neither yes nor no.
3 Photoconsortium	a selection of the crowdsourced photos from All Our Yesterdays (2014) are ingested to Europeana via the Promoter Digital Gallery; the annotations gathered in the Kaleidoscope project are published under the relevant records in Europeana

2.3. How many items from these crowdsourcing initiatives are currently held by your domain/thematic aggregation repository?

Survey responses

Organisation		None	<100	100-500	500-1000	1000-5000	>5000	Not answered
2 Photoconsortium								

Table 11: Number of crowdsourcing items held in national aggregation repository

2.4. How many items from these crowdsourcing initiatives have been ingested from you by Europeana?

Survey responses

Organisation	Number of items
1 CARARE	0
2 Photoconsortium	8600

Table 12: Number of crowdsourcing initiatives ingested by Europeana

2.5. What are the main types of content involved?

Survey responses

Organisation	Photographic images	Artworks or graphical	Text	Data	Sound	Video	3D	Social media posts	Other
1 CARARE									
2 Photoconsortium									

Table 13: Types of content

Organisation	Other
2 Photoconsortium	Annotations

2.6. What factors (if any) stand in the way of ingesting from crowdsourcing activities?

Survey responses

Organisation	We are not always aware of them	Our policies/ strategies do not include them	There is not enough time or resource to include them in our portfolio	Difficulties or certainties associated with technical issues, licensing, metadata or	Other
1 CARARE					
2 Photoconsortium					

Table 14: Factors affecting ingestion from crowdsourcing activities

2.7. Would you be willing to participate in a short follow-up interview about this subject?

Organisation	Yes	No
1 CARARE		
2 Photoconsortium		

Annex 3 – survey of external crowdsourcing projects and activities

3.1. Respondents

Country	Organisation	What is the name of your crowdsourcing project?	What is the topic scope of your crowdsourcing project?
1. Austria	ICARUS International Center for Archival Research	Topotheque	Collecting and Presenting Private Historic Sources
2. Belgium	National Archives	DemoGenVisu	Analysis of the belgian civil status
3. Belgium	meemoo: Flemish Institute for Archive	Various activities to crowdsource images, data and content through Wikimedia platforms	moveable heritage
4. Bulgaria	Institute for Creative Civil Strategies	Cultural Heritage Reporters	Valorization of the cultural heritage of North-East Bulgaria
5. Cyprus	Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports and Youth / Cultural Services - Cyprus Library	There is no specific name. The Cyprus Library administrates the Cyprus Library Digital Platform, an open source digital repository where various Institutions have the ability to register and host their digital collections as part of their crowdsourcing projects from time to time.	There is no specific topic. All Crowdsourcing projects from all Institutions have various topics depending on each Institution's nature and content.
6. Denmark	DR	Historical press photos	A collection of 138.000 old photos from the archives of DR had no or very rare metadata. We invited people to tag persons, things and data about the event on the digitized photos. The crowdsourced tags are searchable.

Country	Organisation	What is the name of your crowdsourcing project?	What is the topic scope of your crowdsourcing project?
7. Estonia	Estonian Photographic Heritage Society ((MTÜ Eesti Fotopärand)	Ajapaik	Enriching PICTORIAL content (mostly historic photographs) with additional metadata and rephotographs.
8. Finland	City of Helsinki	Albumit auki (open albums)	Digitizing old paper based home archives (photographs)
9. Finland	Museovirasto	Plus/Miinus Talvi	Co-participating and collecting photo material and stories
10. Greece	National Technical University of Athens	CrowdHeritage	Cultural Heritage
11. Greece	University of Patras	Culture Gate	Collecting and disseminating tangible and intangible cultural heritage
12. Greece-Ukraine	Freelance Multimedia Project Developer,	General Theme - Cultural Memory	20th century totalitarian regimes, Refugees and Migration, Transatlantic Slave Trade
13. Ireland	Gaois research group, Dublin City University	Meitheal Dúchas.ie	Irish folklore
14. Ireland	Dublin City University	Meitheal Logainm.ie	Toponymy
15. Latvia	Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art (University of Latvia)	iesaisties.lv	folklore, ethnography, photography, local histories, communities, biographies, archive, ethnomusicology
16. Netherlands	Radboud University Nijmegen	multiple projects all centering around transcriptions of Dutch texts, mainly from the Renaissance	transcriptions of Dutch texts, mainly from the Renaissance, but also older and younger
17. Norway	The National Library of Norway	Marianne Wiig	Local history
18. Norway	National Archives of Norway	Census 1920	Transcribe the 1920 census to make it search online

Country	Organisation	What is the name of your crowdsourcing project?	What is the topic scope of your crowdsourcing project?
19. Peru	Theory of construction of the Giza plateau pyramids	Theory of construction of the Giza plateau pyramids	A new Theory of construction of the Giza plateau pyramids which had been accepted by Egyptians already: they invited me to expose it in the CAH (Conservation of Architectural Heritage) conference, hosted yearly by the prestigious and international institute IEREK, and I am seeking for sponsorship to attend.
20. Portugal	University of Coimbra (Herbarium)	EXPLORATOR	herbarium specimens: labels transcription
21. Slovenia	Arctur	Heritage in action	Bread-making
22. Spain	FUNDACION UXIO NOVONEYRA	ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA	LITERARY ARCHIVES
23. Sweden	Wikimedia Sverige	GLAMWiki-collaboration (ongoing activity, not a project)	<p>How GLAMs can work with the Wikimedia movement and communities to reach and engage more people. For most GLAMs working with the Wikimedia community on the Wikimedia platforms is about increasing their audience reach and providing raw materials for volunteers to contextualise in Wikipedia articles, but GLAMs increasingly work with Wikimedians in order to enrich their own collections data, see eg. https://diff.wikimedia.org/2019/12/13/data-roundtripping-a-new-frontier-for-glam-wiki-collaborations/</p> <p>The work is typically centred around the GLAMs collections and will, again typically, involve publishing metadata and mediafiles for parts of the GLAM's collection, or the entire collection, on Wikimedia platforms such as Wikidata, Wikimedia Commons, and Wikipedia. Platforms where the public can then work to update, translate, and enrich the information, metadata or media files. The nature of the collaboration varies with the GLAM, their collection and their particular goals with the collaboration. A core aspect of this work is to advocate for open licensing of GLAM-content, a prerequisite for using the Wikimedia platforms.</p>

Country	Organisation	What is the name of your crowdsourcing project?	What is the topic scope of your crowdsourcing project?
			Note that Sweden is by no means the only Wikimedia chapter to work with GLAMWiki-collaboration - it's a global format. To get a sense of the scope take a look at the monthly This Month in GLAM-newsletter, https://outreach.wikimedia.org/wiki/GLAM/Newsletter which is written by Wikimedia volunteers. In the latest issue alone, and limiting ourselves to Europe, there are reports from projects run in Albania, France, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Serbia, Sweden, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom.
24. Switzerland	ETH Zürich, ETH Library, Image Archive	E-Pics Image Archive Online and sMapshot	Improvement of image descriptions and Georeferencing
25. Ukraine	State Institution "Institute of World History of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine"	The conference for PhD students and the young researchers	Science: mainly - the World History, but also, Philosophy, Law and the History of Ukraine. We needed to coordinate and join all young researcher in the early day of the quarantine to participate in it
26. United Kingdom	UCL	Monument Monitor	To see to what extent we can use visitors' photographs to monitor remote heritage sites. Specifically, what reliable and measurable conservation information can we get from such crowdsourced data.
27. United Kingdom	University of Oxford	Lockdown 2020	Life under lockdown for University of Oxford members

Table 15: List of respondents for Survey 3

Figure 7: Participating countries

3.2. What is the geographic scope of your crowdsourcing project?

Overview

Figure 8: Geographic scope

Additional Comments

Country	What is the name of your crowdsourcing project?	If regional/local please provide details
4 Bulgaria	Cultural Heritage Reporters	Northeast Bulgaria
5 Cyprus	Cyprus Library Digital Platform	The repository is open for all memory Institutions around Cyprus regions.
12 Greece-Ukraine	General Theme - Cultural Memory	CEE,Balkans, Africa

17	Norway	Marianne Wiig	The site covers all of Norway.
21	Slovenia	Heritage in action	Ajdovščina - Vipava Valley
22	Spain	ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA	GALICIA/MADRID
23	Sweden	GLAMWiki- collaboration (ongoing activity, not a project)	Most of our ongoing work is with Swedish GLAMs. We also work with UNESCO Archives and participate in EU-funded projects.
26	United Kingdom	Monument Monitor	Scotland, 20 case study sites across Scotland to gather different information for the several different types of heritage sites, on the scale of very rural to very urban
27	United Kingdom	Lockdown 2020	University of Oxford

	Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
1	Topotheque	Topotheque can go international, translation of interface is provided
2	DemoGenVisu	
5	Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.	The Cyprus Library Digital Platform is currently hosting many digital collections that resulted from local/regional crowdsourcing projects.
7	Ajapaik	The platform is generic and open for content from all over the world, but actual user base is mostly from Estonia and Finland
19	Giza plateau pyramids	You can check my personal blog (https://theory-construction-giza-pyramids.blogspot.com), where you will find all the necessary information, and may contact me directly to my email (crvcrv21@gmail.com, crvcrv21@yahoo.com) or by phone (WhatsApp included): +51-934932462. Thanks a lot. Yours, Prof. Carlos.
23	GLAMWiki - collaboration	The answer above is for Wikimedia Sverige specifically. GLAMWiki-collaboration in general is part of the global Wikimedia movement.
24	E-Pics and sMapshot	We have volunteers from all over the world, but mainly from Switzerland
25	PhD conference	It was firstly organised as national. but some of students invited guests from Poland, so we can called it European) or crosscultural
27	Lockdown 2020	Open to all members of the university irrespective of where they are located during the corona virus lockdown

3.3. What were the funding sources for your crowdsourcing project?

Overview

Figure 9: Funding sources

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
1 Topotheque	Income vs. Funding: Our partners, the municipalities, pay for the service. So you may also call it funding.
6 Historical press photos	I'm not sure if I ticked the correct answer. It was funded inside the corporation.
10 CrowdHeritage	CEF project
12 Cultural Memory	I am unemployed and in search for funding for my multimedia podcast project
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie	Majority funding is from the Irish government
19 Giza plateau pyramids	I had received just minimal quantities from some minor sponsors
20 EXPLORATOR	The project was not funded directly. It was built as a side project by one person on a wider scope project.
21 Heritage in action	Slovenian Research Agency
23 GLAMWiki-collaboration	Again, the answer is for our GLAMwiki collaboration in general, not for a specific project (of which there are too many to answer this survey individually).
26 Monument Monitor	EPSRC (UK Research Institute) and National Heritage organisation joint funded PhD
27 Lockdown 2020	Funded by the Higher Education Innovation Fund and ESRC Impact Acceleration Account through the University of Oxford, 'COVID-19: Economic, Social, Cultural, & Environmental Impacts - Urgent Response Fund'

3.4. What is/was the duration of your crowdsourcing project?

Overview

Figure 10: Duration of crowdsourcing project

Additional comments

	Project/Activity	Please give start date (if known)	Please give end date (if known)	Duration	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
1	Topotheque	01/01/2011		Ongoing	Topotheque is not a project but an infrastructure without end date.
2	DemoGenVisu	01/01/2008			
3	Meemoo				
4	Cultural Herit.Reporters	05/01/2019	01/03/2020	1 year, 1 month	-
5	Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.			Ongoing	There is no actual date for specific crowdsourcing project. All crowdsourcing projects are running simultaneously from various Institutions
6	Historical press photos	01/06/2016			
7	Ajapaik	27/02/2011		Ongoing	The project/platform is ongoing and in constant development
8	Albumit auki	01/01/2003		Ongoing	Ongoing, but no funding now
9	Plus/Miinus Talvi	01/03/2020	01/06/2020	3months	
10	CrowdHeritage	01/09/2018	29/02/2020	1 year, 5 months	
11	Culture Gate	01/05/2015			

Project/Activity	Please give start date (if known)	Please give end date (if known)	Duration	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
12 Cultural Memory	08/04/2020	30/12/2020	8 months	It could be extended
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie	01/01/2015	31/12/2022	7 years, 1 months	We hope to continue after the end of 2022, the current funding round.
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie	14/04/2016		Ongoing	Ongoing
15 iesaisties.lv	01/10/2014		Ongoing	The crowdsourcing platform and campaigns are ongoing.
16 Netherlands - projects	01/07/2007	10/08/2020	13 years, 1month	I have done multiple projects continuously from 2007 onwards till now, partly with the same crowd, partly with new members
17 Marianne Wiig	16/10/2007		Ongoing	The start date is an approximation. We went out of beta in March 2008.
18 Census 1920	01/10/2018	01/12/2020	2 years, 2 months	
19 Giza plateau pyramids	09/03/2003	31/12/2021	18 years, 9 months	I hope to find some sponsor(s) from person(s) or entity(ies) this year to, finally, attend to one of IEREK-¥s conferences they invited me to expose my theory: the CAH or CITAA conferences
20 EXPLORATOR	22/04/2020			The project will remain permanently active
21 Heritage in action	01/11/2019	31/07/2021	1 year, 8 months	
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA	01/01/2016			
23 GLAMWiki collaboration				Not filling this in as we're not providing information about a specific project. We've been doing GLAMwiki-collaboration since at least 2010.
24 E-Pics and sMapshot	01/01/2010		Ongoing	It is an ongoing process with a daily routine in the Image Archive
25 PhD conference		16/06/2020		16 of June it was the Date of the conference "Modern Problems of History, Philosophy and Law in the Research of Young Scientists"
26 Monument Monitor	01/10/2018	15/09/2021	2 years, 11months	Length of PhD

Project/Activity	Please give start date (if known)	Please give end date (if known)	Duration	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
27 Lockdown 2020	15/04/2020		Ongoing	Accepts submissions relating to any time from March 2020

Table 16: Duration of project/activity and supporting comments

3.5. What are/were the main aims of your crowdsourcing project?

Overview

Figure 11: Aims of crowdsourcing project

Survey responses

Project/Activity	Broadcast search – solving a	Community engagement/ participation	Create common goods	Distributed human intelligence	Knowledge discovery and management	Peer-vetted creative production –	Preservation/ documentatio n	Other
1 Topotheque								
2 DemoGenVisu								
3 Meemoo								
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters								
5 Cyprus-Library Digital Plt.								
6 Historical press photos								
7 Ajapaik								
8 Albumit auki								
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi								
10 CrowdHeritage								
11 Culture Gate								
12 Cultural Memory								

Project/Activity	Broadcast search – solving a	Community engagement/ participation	Create common goods	Distributed human intelligence	Knowledge discovery and management	Peer-vetted creative production –	Preservation/ documentation	Other
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie								
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie								
15 iesaisties.lv								
16 Netherlands - projects								
17 Marianne Wiig								
18 Census 1920								
19 Giza plateau pyramids								
20 EXPLORATOR								
21 Heritage in action								
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA								
23 GLAMWiki collaboration								
24 E-Pics and sMapshot								
25 PhD conference								
26 Monument Monitor								
27 Lockdown 2020								

Table 17: Aims of crowdsourcing project

Question responses to ‘Other’ option

Project/Activity	Other
3 Meemoo	assessing public support
10 CrowdHeritage	CH metadata enrichment
11 Culture Gate	Education
12 Cultural Memory	Support of vulnerable social groups during COVID pandemic induced social isolation
19 Giza plateau pyramids	Eliminate the misunderstanding of the Giza plateau pyramids problem of how were made, finally
20 EXPLORATOR	Transcription
23 GLAMWiki – collaboration	The goal of the Wikimedia movement is to provide free knowledge to everyone. The goal of participating GLAMs is typically to educate and inform the public on the basis of their collections.
25 PhD conference	Eliminate the misunderstanding of the Giza plateau pyramids problem of how were made, finally

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie	We are inviting users of the site to transcribe, on a voluntary basis, folklore and local history collected in the 1930s. We hope that this work will increase community participation in the project and that it will improve accessibility of the material as well.
16 Netherlands - projects	the main reason is that I need reliable data and metadata for my research and want to share this with others in open access. It is too much work to make these data accessible without the crowd
19 Giza plateau pyramids	Eliminate the misunderstanding of the Giza plateau pyramids problem of how were made, finally
24 E-Pics and sMapshot	Improvement of image description, identification of unknown places/people/objects, georeferencing of images

3.6. What activities have you carried out in the project?

Overview

Figure 12: Project activities

Survey responses

Project/Activity	Collect digitised objects or data	Collectively build digital artefacts (e.g. 3D models)	Convert analogue to digital (digitisation)	Edit or enhance, improve quality	Evaluate digital items/ research data	Prepare data/ metadata for aggregation	Process/ analyse/ interpret information or datasets	Transcription	Other
1 Topotheque									
2 DemoGenVisu									
3 Meemoo									
4 Cultural Herit. Reporters									
5 Cyprus-Library Digital									
6 Historical press photos									
7 Ajapaik									

Project/Activity	Collect digitised objects or data	Collectively build digital artefacts (e.g. 3D models)	Convert analogue to digital (digitisation)	Edit or enhance, improve quality	Evaluate digital items/ research data	Prepare data/metadata for aggregation	Process/ analyse/ interpret information or datasets	Transcription	Other
8 Albumit auki									
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi									
10 CrowdHeritage									
11 Culture Gate									
12 Cultural Memory									
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie									
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie									
15 iesaisties.lv									
16 Netherlands - projects									
17 Marianne Wiig									
18 Census 1920									
19 Giza plateau pyramids									
20 EXPLORATOR									
21 Heritage in action									
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA									
23 GLAMWiki colloboration									
24 E-Pics and sMapshot									
25 PhD conference									
26 Monument Monitor									
27 Lockdown 2020									

Table 18: Project activities

Question responses to 'Other' option

Project/Activity	Other
4 Cultural Herit. Rep.	participatory heritage through non-formal education and peer learning,
7 Ajapaik	geotagging, rephotography
12 Cultural Memory	Create summaries and stories and making podcasts
19 Giza plateau pyramids	editing and translating the content of my theory
24 E-Pics and sMapshot	Georeferencing of images

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
27 Lockdown 202	Collecting media (images, audio, video) and text ('About my day' 'Message to the future')

3.7. What type of organisation facilitates/coordinates the project?

Overview

Figure 13: Type of facilitating/ coordinating organisation

Survey responses

Project/Activity	Archive	Community organisation	Gallery	Government body	Higher education	Individual	Library	Museum	NGO	Private sponsor	Research organisation	Standalone initiative	Other
1 Topotheque													
2 DemoGenVisu													
3 Meemoo													
4 Cultural													
5 Cyprus- ibrary Digital													
6 Historical press													
7 Ajapaik													
8 Albumit auki													
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi													
10 CrowdHeritage													
11 Culture Gate													
12 Cultural Memory													
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie													
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie													
15 iesaisties.lv													
16 Netherlands -													
17 Marianne Wiig													

Project/Activity	Archive	Community organisation	Gallery	Government body	Higher education	Individual	Library	Museum	NGO	Private sponsor	Research organisation	Standalone initiative	Other
18 Census 1920	■												
19 Giza plateau						■						■	
20 EXPLORATOR					■						■		
21 Heritage in action											■		
22 ARQUIVO	■					■		■					
23 GLAMWiki	■			■			■	■	■				
24 E-Pics and sMapshot	■				■		■						
25 PhD conference				■	■	■					■		■
26 Monument Monitor				■	■								
27 Lockdown 2020					■								

Table 19: Type of facilitating/coordinating organisation

Question responses to 'Other' option

Project/Activity	Other
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.	Local Authorities
10 CrowdHeritage	Technical expert (university - computer science school)
25 PhD conference	we are the State Institution the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
1 Topotheque	Topotheque has coordination on 2 levels: Top: Organization of all Topotheques by ICARUS, Organization of individual Topotheques by municipalities or local archives or museums
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie	A collaboration between two Irish universities
15 iesaisties.lv	The Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art (University of Latvia) is a research organization that includes the Archives of Latvian Folklore.
17 Marianne Wiig	The Norwegian Institute of Local History (NGO) became a part of The National Library in 2016.

3.8. What was the mode of collection?

Overview

Figure 14: Mode of collection

Survey responses

	Project/Activity	Analogue	Mobile	Social Media	Web-based	Other
1	Topotheque					
2	DemoGenVisu					
3	Meemoo					
4	Cultural Herit.Reporters					
5	Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.					
6	Historical press photos					
7	Ajapaik					
8	Albumit auki					
9	Plus/Miinus Talvi					
10	CrowdHeritage					
11	Culture Gate					
12	Cultural Memory					
13	Meitheal Dúchas.ie					
14	Meitheal Logainm.ie					
15	iesasties.lv					
16	Netherlands - projects					
17	Marianne Wiig					
18	Census 1920					
19	Giza plateau pyramids					
20	EXPLORATOR					
21	Heritage in action					
22	ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA					

	Project/Activity	Analogue	Mobile	Social Media	Web-based	Other
23	GLAMWiki colloboration					
24	E-Pics and sMapshot					
25	PhD conference					
26	Monument Monitor					
27	Lockdown 2020					

Table 20: Mode of collection

Question responses to 'Other' option

	Project/Activity	Other
12	Cultural Memory	Interviews
19	Giza plateau pyramids	Forums, libraries, etc.

Additional comments

	Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
7	Ajapaik	In addition to web app there is also android application for rephotography
8	Albumit auki	Database with API
15	iesasties.lv	I am not sure if I understood the question correctly. The main material in question was collected by analogue means. Now the new material is collected digitally.
23	GLAMWiki collaboration	The Wikimedia platforms are all developed to work at least decently on mobile devices. For some there are official mobile applications.

3.9. What tasks were crowdsourced?

Overview

Figure 15: Crowdsourced tasks

Survey responses

Project/Activity	Audio transcription	Autotagging/recognition	Captcha	Categorisation	Classification	Counting 'likes'	Digital art	Digitising/uploading	Error checking/cleaning	Gaming	Geoconferencing	Indexing	Linking	Photo-masking	Ranking algorithms	Tagging/annotation	Other
1 Topotheque				█				█			█	█	█			█	
2 DemoGenVisu												█					
3 Meemoo				█				█								█	
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters				█	█		█	█					█	█		█	
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.								█	█			█					
6 Historical press photos																█	
7 Ajapaik				█				█			█					█	█
8 Albumit auki		█						█			█					█	

Project/Activity	Audio transcription	Autotagging/recognition	Captcha	Categorisation	Classification	Counting 'likes'	Digital art	Digitising/uploading	Error checking/cleaning	Gaming	Geoconferencing	Indexing	Linking	Photo-masking	Ranking algorithms	Tagging/annotation	Other
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi																	
10 CrowdHeritage																	
11 Culture Gate																	
12 Cultural Memory																	
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie																	
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie																	
15 iesaisties.lv																	
16 Netherlands - projects																	
17 Marianne Wiig																	
18 Census 1920																	
19 Giza plateau pyramids																	
20 EXPLORATOR																	
21 Heritage in action																	
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA																	
23 GLAMWiki collaboration																	
24 E-Pics and sMapshot																	
25 PhD conference																	
26 Monument Monitor																	
27 Lockdown 2020																	

Table 21: Crowdsourced tasks

Question responses to 'Other' option

Project/Activity	Other
7 Ajapaik	Rephotography (crowdsourcing contemporary repeat photos of views on historic images)
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie	Transcription of manuscripts
16 Netherlands - projects	Transcription, for instance of all 17th century Dutch newspapers = 18 million words

17	Marianne Wiig	Writing articles
20	EXPLORATOR	Transcription
23	GLAMWiki collaboration	Translation of descriptive metadata, Text transcription/OCR correction, Photographic documentation (of cultural and natural heritage environments and objects), Writing of encyclopedic articles
26	Monument Monitor	Taking photographs
27	Lockdown 2020	Data creation (text written specifically for collection, on platform)

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
10 CrowdHeritage	The platform supports (i) addition of new annotations, notably selection of thesauri terms relevant to some CH object (ii) validation (up/down-voting) of annotations added by some automatic algorithm (e.g. color detection) or by other participants.

3.10. What types of content were collected?

Overview

Figure 16: Types of content collected

Survey responses

Project/Activity	3D	AR/VR	Archival or text-based	Cultural artifacts	Online data	Online metadata	Photographs	Social media posts	Sound	Video	Web archives	Other
1 Topotheque												
2 DemoGenVisu												
3 Meemoo												
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters												
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.												
6 Historical press photos												
7 Ajapaik												
8 Albumit auki												
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi												
10 CrowdHeritage												
11 Culture Gate												
12 Cultural Memory												
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie												
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie												
15 iesaisties.lv												
16 Netherlands - projects												
17 Marianne Wiig												
18 Census 1920												
19 Giza plateau pyramids												
20 EXPLORATOR												
21 Heritage in action												
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA												
23 GLAMWiki collaboration												
24 E-Pics and sMapshot												
25 PhD conference												
26 Monument Monitor												
27 Lockdown 2020												

Table 22: Types of content collected

Question responses to 'Other' option

Project/Activity	Other
7 Ajapaik	Our focus is pictorial content , - while photographs dominate we also include paintings and graphic art
12 Cultural Memory	Broadcasted interviews
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie	Lexical items, i.e. minor placenames (text and/or audio)
20 EXPLORATOR	Herbarium specimens

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
6 Historical press photos	I'm not sure that I ticked the right answer. The photos are in a database, and the users can tag metadata directly on the photos.

3.11. What supporting events were organised (online or physical)?

Overview

Figure 17: Organised supporting events

Survey responses

Project/Activity	Continuous	Hackathon	Research/fieldwork	Roadshow	Transcribathon	Other
1 Topotheque	1	0	0	0	0	1
2 DemoGenVisu	0	0	0	0	0	0
3 Meemoo	0	0	0	0	0	1
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters	0	0	1	0	0	1
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.	1	0	1	0	1	0
6 Historical press photos	0	0	0	1	0	1

Project/Activity	Continuous	Hackathon	Research/ fieldwork	Roadshow	Transcribatho n	Other
7 Ajapaik						
8 Albumit auki						
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi						
10 CrowdHeritage						
11 Culture Gate						
12 Cultural Memory						
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie						
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie						
15 iesaisties.lv						
16 Netherlands - projects						
17 Marianne Wiig						
18 Census 1920						
19 Giza plateau pyramids						
20 EXPLORATOR						
21 Heritage in action						
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA						
23 GLAMWiki colloboration						
24 E-Pics and sMapshot						
25 PhD conference						
26 Monument Monitor						
27 Lockdown 2020						

Table 23: Organised supporting events

Question responses to 'Other' option

Project/Activity	Other
1 Topotheque	User workshops to improve quality of digitizing and annotation
3 Meemoo	Photo contest, edit-a-thon
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters	Photo and video documentation
6 Historical press photos	Several articles about how many tags people give us.
10 CrowdHeritage	Digital crowd-/nichesourcing campaigns + workshops (physical)
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie	Talks at various events, during Heritage Week, at libraries, to students, etc
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie	Occasional workshops

15	iesasties.lv	Publicity campaigns (in cooperation with national-scale media); task-force campaigns, competitions
16	Netherlands - projects	Written instructions, feedback through form or mail, lecture once a year
17	Marianne Wiig	Workshops, seminars and online guidance.
23	GLAMWiki collaboration	Editathons (=time limited intensive and collaborative editing of Wikipedia articles, Wikimedia Commons file metadata, etc.), Photography campaigns (Wiki Loves Monuments, Wiki Loves Earth))
27	Lockdown 2020	Identifying and contacting specific individuals directly (online); social media campaign

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.	In most cases the Cyprus Library Digital Platform administrators gave access to local authorities to submit their own datasets along with the respective content (metadata). This procedure was conducted via online communication between the two parties
23 GLAMWiki Collaboration	We've mostly partnered with others in arranging hackathons, eg with the Swedish National Heritage Board.

3.12. What was the context for the project?

Overview

Figure 18: Project context

Survey responses

Project/Activity	Citizen Science	Storytelling	Wikidata	Other
1 Topotheque				
2 DemoGenVisu				
3 Meemoo				
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters				
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.				
6 Historical press photos				
7 Ajapaik				

Project/Activity	Citizen Science	Storytelling	Wikidata	Other
8 Albumit auki				
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi				
10 CrowdHeritage				
11 Culture Gate				
12 Cultural Memory				
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie				
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie				
15 iesaisties.lv				
16 Netherlands - projects				
17 Marianne Wiig				
18 Census 1920				
19 Giza plateau pyramids				
20 EXPLORATOR				
21 Heritage in action				
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA				
23 GLAMWiki colloboration				
24 E-Pics and sMapshot				
25 PhD conference				
26 Monument Monitor				
27 Lockdown 2020				

Table 24: Project context

Question responses to 'Other' option

Project/Activity	Other
6 Historical press photos	To help DR with searchable metadata in a collection formerly very difficult to navigate in
10 CrowdHeritage	Nichesourcing (mobilising crowds of CH professionals, culture lovers, creators etc in CH different fields)
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie	I don't understand this question.
19 Giza plateau pyramids	Forums, websites, emails
23 GLAMWiki colloboration	Collaborative editing of encyclopedias, Sharing of educational information related to heritage, Awareness raising in regards to cultural and natural heritage, Writing Wikipedia articles as part of school lessons
25 PhD conference	History
27 Lockdown 2020	Create a record of experiences of this special time

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
7 Ajapaik	We're only starting with the integration with Wikidata (and also Wikimedia Commons)
18 Census 1920	Transcribe the 1920 census to make it search online.

3.13. Were any of the following technical framework or tools employed?

Overview

Figure 19: Technical framework or tools employed

Survey responses

Project/Activity	CrowdHeritage	Enrich Europeana	Metadata games	OAI-PMH	Pybossa	Zooniverse	Offline tools	None	Other
1 Topotheque									
2 DemoGenVisu									
3 Meemoo									
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters									
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.									
6 Historical press photos									
7 Ajapaik									
8 Albumit auki									
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi									
10 CrowdHeritage									

Project/Activity	CrowdHeritage	Enrich Europeana	Metadata games	OAI-PMH	Pybossa	Zooniverse	Offline tools	None	Other
11 Culture Gate									
12 Cultural Memory									
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie									
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie									
15 iesaisties.lv									
16 Netherlands - projects									
17 Marianne Wiig									
18 Census 1920									
19 Giza plateau pyramids									
20 EXPLORATOR									
21 Heritage in action									
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA									
23 GLAMWiki collaboration									
24 E-Pics and sMapshot									
25 PhD conference									
26 Monument Monitor									
27 Lockdown 2020									

Table 25: Technical framework or tools employed

Question responses to 'Other' option

Project/Activity	Other
12 Cultural Memory	Europeana Migration
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie	We used our own systems.
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie	We built our own web-based collection tool
16 Netherlands - projects	Platforms built at my research institute
17 Marianne Wiig	Wikimedia platform.
18 Census 1920	Using a "Self-made" system
23 GLAMWiki collaboration	Mediawiki incl. its Wikibase extension, Multiple accessory/productivity tools based on the Mediawiki APIs
26 Monument Monitor	Self-built online database
27 Lockdown 2020	Omeka

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
10 CrowdHeritage	This project was about the development of the CrowdHeritage platform. The platform has also been used for setting up and conducting digital crowdsourcing campaigns in the context of the Fifties in Europe Kaleidoscope CEF project. The objectives of the campaigns in the Kaleidoscope project were similar to the ones conducted under CrowdHeritage (engagement, improving CH metadata quality).
20 EXPLORATOR	A new tool was developed specifically for this project.

3.14. How is/was the crowdsourced content stored?

Overview

Figure 20: Content storage

Survey responses

Project/Activity	Internal repository	Cloud-based	Other
1 Topotheque			
2 DemoGenVisu			
3 Meemoo			
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters			
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.			
6 Historical press photos			
7 Ajapaik			
8 Albumit auki			
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi			
10 CrowdHeritage			
11 Culture Gate			
12 Cultural Memory			
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie			
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie			

15	iesasties.lv			
16	Netherlands - projects			
17	Marianne Wiig			
18	Census 1920			
19	Giza plateau pyramids			
20	EXPLORATOR			
21	Heritage in action			
22	ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA			
23	GLAMWiki collaboration			
24	E-Pics and sMapshot			
25	PhD conference			
26	Monument Monitor			
27	Lockdown 2020			

Table 26: Content storage

Question responses to 'Other' option

	Project/Activity	Other
8	Albumit auki	Database
10	CrowdHeritage	Europeana
23	GLAMWiki collaboration	Contributed data is stored on Wikimedia servers. These are primarily located in the US.

Additional comments

	Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
1	Topotheque	Server in EU
10	CrowdHeritage	The platform is linked to Europeana: the enrichments are posted as annotations to Europeana or as part of the EDM accompanying CH objects
23	GLAMWiki collaboration	Some GLAMs we work with choose to include user-created metadata and links added to their content on the Wikimedia platforms in their own databases. This can be eg. improved, translated or corrected metadata. It's becoming increasingly common to align Wikidata-object URIs with GLAM's own vocabularies, see eg https://wikimedia.se/2020/06/10/kulturnav-a-hub-for-museum-vocabularies-connected-to-wikidata/

3.15. Were any of the following metadata and identifier standards employed?

Overview

Figure 21: Metadata and identifier standards employed

Survey responses

Project/Activity	DOI	Dublin Core	EAD	EDM	FOAF	Getty Vocabularie	IIF	METS	Shcema.org	Home-grown	Persistent identifier	None	Other
	1 Topotheque		■										
2 DemoGenVisu												■	
3 Meemoo						■							
4 Cultural												■	
5 Cyprus - Library Digital		■											
6 Historical press photos												■	
7 Ajapaik													
8 Albumit auki		■											
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi													
10 CrowdHeritage				■		■							
11 Culture Gate												■	
12 Cultural Memory													
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie		■								■	■		
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie										■	■		
15 iesaisties.lv												■	
16 Netherlands - projects											■		
17 Marianne Wiig	■										■		■
18 Census 1920										■	■		

Project/Activity	DOI	Dublin Core	EAD	EDM	FOAF	Getty Vocabulary	IIF	METS	Shcema.org	Home-grown	Persistent identifier	None	Other
19 Giza plateau pyramids													
20 EXPLORATOR													
21 Heritage in action													
22 ARQUIVO													
23 GLAMWiki													
24 E-Pics and sMapshot													
25 PhD conference													
26 Monument Monitor													
27 Lockdown 2020													

Table 27: Metadata and identifier standards employed

Question responses to 'Other' option

Project/Activity	Other
17 Marianne Wiig	Wikidata, VIAF
27 Lockdown 2020	Sub-set of Dublin Core

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.	The Repository has a prefixed Dublin Core schema. In case of mapping metadata schemas for the purpose of hosting more content this is being conducted via internal modifications in the system.
7 Ajapaik	We ingest content from multiple sources (repositories), but have not been consistent with using metadata standards
10 CrowdHeritage	The platform supports multiple established vocabularies and thesauri. When the user sets up a campaign, they can select the vocabularies that they wish to use.
17 Marianne Wiig	Each internal entry has permanent links. We also link to persistent external identifiers.
23 GLAMWiki collaboration	Varies from GLAM to GLAM. File formats are often standard (XML, CSV) but data models vary. There are a number of tools for wrangling and batch uploading data to Wikimedia Commons and Wikidata, as long as the in-file format is, or can be converted to, XML or CSV we can work with it.

3.16. How was the metadata created or generated?

Overview

Figure 22: Creation or generation of metadata

Survey responses

Project/Activity	Manually created	Captured from external source	Auto-generated	Other
1 Topotheque				
2 DemoGenVisu				
3 Meemoo				
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters				
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.				
6 Historical press photos				
7 Ajapaik				
8 Albumit auki				
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi				
10 CrowdHeritage				
11 Culture Gate				
12 Cultural Memory				
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie				
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie				
15 iesaisties.lv				
16 Netherlands - projects				
17 Marianne Wiig				
18 Census 1920				
19 Giza plateau pyramids				
20 EXPLORATOR				
21 Heritage in action				
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA				
23 GLAMWiki colloboration				
24 E-Pics and sMapshot				
25 PhD conference				
26 Monument Monitor				
27 Lockdown 2020				

Table 28: Creation or generation of metadata

Question responses to 'Other' option

Project/Activity	Other
27 Lockdown 2020	Participants entered

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
1 Topotheque	Creating metadata individually is the social side of Toptheque: inviting people on a local basis to enrich metadata.
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.	In some cases, the Repository uses prefixed metadata fields which are generated by the system.
10 CrowdHeritage	In case of validation, the annotations were added by some automatic AI algorithm (e.g. for object detection, color detection) and participants were invited to down-/up-vote them.
23 GLAMWiki collaboration	<p>"The original data comes from the GLAM's Collections Management System or equivalent. We assume that is what is mean by ""captured from external source"" above (?).</p> <p>Some metadata is autogenerated as the batch upload is being prepared. These are typically administrative metadata, Wikimedia Commons categories, language tags, and copyright statements.</p> <p>For batch uploads manually created data is added post-upload to the Wikimedia platforms. "</p>

3.17. What was the quantity of crowdsourced items collected?

Overview

Figure 23: Quantity of crowdsourced items collected

Survey responses (from open text)

Project/Activity		Digital objects	Metadata records	User interventions (tags etc.)
1	Topotheque	720	720	1550000
2	DemoGenVisu	0	2495434	0
3	Meemoo			
4	Cultural Herit.Reporters	6000	200	3000
5	Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.	650	1800	300
6	Historical press photos			
7	Ajapaik	200000	184700	300000
8	Albumit auki	4000		
9	Plus/Miinus Talvi	80	10	10
10	CrowdHeritage	7000	7000	100000
11	Culture Gate	5000	8000	
12	Cultural Memory			
13	Meitheal Dúchas.ie	300000		
14	Meitheal Logainm.ie	47200		
15	iesasties.lv			
16	Netherlands - projects	1000000	100	
17	Marianne Wiig			
18	Census 1920	705	2115	27576
19	Giza plateau pyramids	21	12	700
20	EXPLORATOR	7500	33000	100000
21	Heritage in action	200	200	0
22	ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA			
23	GLAMWiki collaboration	25000	25000	
24	E-Pics and sMapshot	200000	200000	2000000
25	PhD conference			
26	Monument Monitor	4000	12000	3000
27	Lockdown 2020	300	150	
Total		1,854,476	2,971,441	2,284,900

Table 29: Quantity of crowdsourced items collected

Additional comments

	Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
1	Topotheque	A metadata record corresponds to a digital object. Intervention: 1.5 Million tags created by Citizen Scientists.
6	Historical press photos	The number is rising because the project is still running
7	Ajapaik	~270000 geotags submitted, 17300 rephotos + other kind of tags (specifying datings, connecting duplicates, textual comments, transcriptions)
10	CrowdHeritage	6 crowdsourcing campaigns; almost 100.000 tags collected (annotations, upvotes and downvotes) on about 7.000 Europeana records; 218 registrations and 134 active contributors on the platform. More campaigns and data have been collected in the context of other projects (e.g. Kaleidoscope).
12	Cultural Memory	I have been studying data for possible inclusion in project illustration and for learning about stories creation
13	Meitheal Dúchas.ie	300,000 pages of folklore have been transcribed so far.
15	iesaieties.lv	There are different types of results produced by volunteers that cannot be answered as asked. E.g., manuscript transcription platform counts time spent by the volunteers in transcription work. By August 4, 2020, it is 23 300 hours in total.
17	Marianne Wiig	For the most part the wiki consists of encyclopedic articles and images. Our users have created approx. 58 000 content pages and uploaded 180 000 media files. They have also linked to persistent identifiers in external databases: 42 000 (text based), 6 500 (images) 15 000 (georeferences).
18	Census 1920	There are 2757633 list in the 1920 census. One list for every person
23	GLAMWiki collaboration	The digital objects and metadata records already exist - what we do is that we publish them where they can reach a large amount of people. So original digital objects and metadata records are typically not created in our GLAMWiki-collaborations but are published on our open platforms and thus become available for collaborative editing and contextualisation. About 260 000 media files have ben published on Wikimedia Commons as a direct result of our content partnerships with Swedish GLAMs, see https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Wikimedia_Sverige#Opening_and_sharing_free_material . Wiki Loves Monuments Sweden, which has support from the Swedish National Heritage Board, the Museums of Work Secretariat, and the National Maritime Museums, has resulted in 25 200 new/original photographs with associated metadata - importantly always with a reference-link to the monument's ID in the official Swedish Cultural Environments Registry. This allows the National Heritage Board to include links to the photographs in the national aggregator SOCH/K-samsvðk. For all WLM-stats, see https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Wiki_Loves_Monuments
27	Lockdown 2020	Collection still ongoing

3.18. Were any of the following exchange protocols used?

Overview

Figure 24: Exchange protocols used

Survey responses

Project/Activity	OAI-PMH	Resource Sync	SPARQL	SWORD	XML/RDF	None	Other
1 Topotheque	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
2 DemoGenVisu	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No
3 Meemoo	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
6 Historical press photos	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
7 Ajapaik	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
8 Albumit auki	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No
10 CrowdHeritage	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
11 Culture Gate	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
12 Cultural Memory	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
15 iesaisties.lv	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
16 Netherlands - projects	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
17 Marianne Wiig	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
18 Census 1920	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
19 Giza plateau pyramids	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
20 EXPLORATOR	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
21 Heritage in action	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No

Project/Activity	OAI-PMH	Resource Sync	SPARQL	SWORD	XML/RDF	None	Other
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA							
23 GLAMWiki collaboration							
24 E-Pics and sMapshot							
25 PhD conference							
26 Monument Monitor							
27 Lockdown 2020							

Table 30: Exchange protocols used

Question responses to 'Other' option

Project/Activity	Other
6 Historical press photos	I'm not sure
20 EXPLORATOR	JSON
23 GLAMWiki collaboration	We work with whatever data dumps or technical interface a GLAM can offer. If we can work it, we accept it. We set no formal technical requirements but do have hard requirements concerning copyright.

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
10 CrowdHeritage	The system supports the possibility to export data to RDF and search them via a SPARQL endpoint. But this possibility was not used in the context of the CrowdHeritage project.
23 GLAMWiki collaboration	RDF/XML is not an exchange protocol. Nor is SPARQL (though it can be used to fetch data). XML and CSV are the most common formats we receive from the GLAMs, in very few cases does the XML serialize RDF.

3.19. Who were the main participants in crowdsourcing?

Overview

Figure 25: Main crowdsourcing participants

Survey responses

Project/Activity	General population	Children/schools	Higher education/research	Members/frequent users	Professionals	Retired people	Self-employed/casual (paid)	Volunteers	Other
1 Topotheque									
2 DemoGenVisu									
3 Meemoo									
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters									
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.									
6 Historical press photos									
7 Ajapaik									
8 Albumit auki									
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi									
10 CrowdHeritage									
11 Culture Gate									
12 Cultural Memory									
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie									
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie									
15 iesaisties.lv									
16 Netherlands - projects									

Project/Activity	General population	Children/schools	Higher education/research	Members/frequent users	Professionals	Retired people	Self-employed/casual (paid)	Volunteers	Other
17 Marianne Wiig									
18 Census 1920									
19 Giza plateau pyramids									
20 EXPLORATOR									
21 Heritage in action									
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA									
23 GLAMWiki collaboration									
24 E-Pics and sMapshot									
25 PhD conference									
26 Monument Monitor									
27 Lockdown 2020									

Table 31: Main crowdsourcing participants

Question responses to 'Other' option

Project/Activity	Other
10 CrowdHeritage	CH professionals, culture enthusiasts, pupils
26 Monument Monitor	Visitors to heritage sites
27 Lockdown 2020	Members of University of Oxford

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
10 CrowdHeritage	music experts and amateurs; fashion students and scholars as well as fashion lovers/fashionistas; pupils and teachers from elementary/middle/high schools
23 GLAMWiki collaboration	For privacy reasons the Wikimedia movement does a minimum of tracking users. From surveys its known that Wikimedia volunteers skew towards male, white and academic. Paid editing and original research is discouraged,. GLAM-professionals are encouraged to contribute based on their expertise but discouraged from using the Wikimedia platform to "market" their own institution.

3.20. How many participants contributed?

Overview

Figure 26: Number of contributing participants

Survey responses

Project/Activity	0-50	51-100	101-500	501-1000	1001-2000	More than 2000
1 Topotheque						
2 DemoGenVisu						
3 Meemoo						
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters						
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.						
6 Historical press photos						
7 Ajapaik						
8 Albumit auki						
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi						
10 CrowdHeritage						
11 Culture Gate						
12 Cultural Memory						
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie						
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie						
15 iesaisties.lv						
16 Netherlands - projects						
17 Marianne Wiig						
18 Census 1920						
19 Giza plateau pyramids						
20 EXPLORATOR						
21 Heritage in action						
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA						
23 GLAMWiki colloboration						

Project/Activity	0-50	51-100	101-500	501-1000	1001-2000	More than 2000
24 E-Pics and sMapshot						
25 PhD conference						
26 Monument Monitor						
27 Lockdown 2020						

Table 32: Number of contributing participants

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
1 Topotheque	In every municipal Topotheque a lot of Citizens donate their findings. A minimal calculation: 300 Topotheques, take at least 20 people donating: more than 6.000 people.
6 Historical press photos	During the project period we have had 17.700 first time users and 25.200 user sessions
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie	We have c2,500 members, but not all are active. It is also possible to contribute anonymously.
23 GLAMWiki collaboration	Answer limited to Wikimedia Sverige GLAMWiki-collaborations only and very approximate.
27 Lockdown 2020	Collection still open

3.21. What were the main intended motivations for participation?

Overview

Figure 27: Intended motivation for participation

Survey responses

Project/Activity	Contributing to knowledge production	Identity/self-definition	Interest/curiosity	Learning about heritage and history	Promoting locality and place	Skill/career development	Supporting an institution or cause	Other
1 Topotheque								
2 DemoGenVisu								
3 Meemoo								
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters								
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.								
6 Historical press photos								
7 Ajapaik								
8 Albumit auki								
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi								
10 CrowdHeritage								
11 Culture Gate								
12 Cultural Memory								
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie								
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie								
15 iesaisties.lv								

Project/Activity	Contributing to knowledge production	Identity/self-definition	Interest/curiosity	Learning about heritage and history	Promoting locality and place	Skill/career development	Supporting an institution or cause	Other
16 Netherlands - projects								
17 Marianne Wiig								
18 Census 1920								
19 Giza plateau pyramids								
20 EXPLORATOR								
21 Heritage in action								
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA								
23 GLAMWiki colloboration								
24 E-Pics and sMapshot								
25 PhD conference								
26 Monument Monitor								
27 Lockdown 2020								

Table 33: Intended motivation for participation

Question responses to 'Other' option

Project/Activity	Other
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.	Digital Preservation
23 GLAMWiki colloboration	The motivation of individual Wikimedia volunteers vary greatly - all of the above included.
27 Lockdown 2020	Documenting an extraordinary time

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
1 Topotheque	People donating their findings are proud to be part of their community/municipality
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie	Many of the stories are from a particular area or family, so there is usually a strong personal connection.
23 GLAMWiki collaboration	Contributing free knowledge, in all languages, is the goal of the Wikimedia community as a whole. The language aspect is an important motivator for many Wikimedians, perhaps especially so for minority language communities.

3.22. What forms of evaluation were carried out?

Overview

Figure 28: Forms of evaluation carried out

Survey responses

Project/Activity	Validation of user contributions	Formative evaluation	Impact Assessment	Interface heuristics	Outcome harvesting	Output metrics	Summative evaluation
1 Topotheque							
2 DemoGenVisu							
3 Meemoo							
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters							
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.							
6 Historical press photos							
7 Ajapaik							
8 Albumit auki							
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi							
10 CrowdHeritage							
11 Culture Gate							
12 Cultural Memory							
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie							
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie							
15 iesaisties.lv							
16 Netherlands - projects							
17 Marianne Wiig							
18 Census 1920							

Project/Activity	Validation of user contributions	Formative evaluation	Impact Assessment	Interface heuristics	Outcome harvesting	Output metrics	Summative evaluation
19 Giza plateau pyramids							
20 EXPLORATOR							
21 Heritage in action							
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA							
23 GLAMWiki collaboration							
24 E-Pics and sMapshot							
25 PhD conference							
26 Monument Monitor							
27 Lockdown 2020							

Table 34: Forms of evaluation carried out

Additional comments

Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
6 Historical press photos	The tags have been harvested into an internal database (not open to public) which contains all press photos from DR. New user tags will be harvested later on.
7 Ajapaik	Social validation is used, and other users can validate other users contributions, no official validation on the part of the platform.
10 CrowdHeritage	Use of online and printed questionnaires; tools from the Europeana Impact Framework (empathy map and strategic perspectives card).
18 Census 1920	Evaluation will follow after the transcription is finished
23 GLAMWiki collaboration	We also publish white papers, or case studies if you will. Not sure where they fit in the examples above. Example white papers here, https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/FindingGLAMs/White_Paper
27 Lockdown 2020	Analysis ongoing

3.23. Under which licenses was the crowdsourced material made available for use?

Overview

Figure 29: Licenses used

Survey responses

Project/Activity	CC-BY	Other CC	GPL	None	Other
1 Topotheque					
2 DemoGenVisu					
3 Meemoo					
4 Cultural Herit.Reporters					
5 Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.					
6 Historical press photos					
7 Ajapaik					
8 Albumit auki					
9 Plus/Miinus Talvi					
10 CrowdHeritage					
11 Culture Gate					
12 Cultural Memory					
13 Meitheal Dúchas.ie					
14 Meitheal Logainm.ie					
15 iesaisties.lv					
16 Netherlands - projects					
17 Marianne Wiig					
18 Census 1920					
19 Giza plateau pyramids					
20 EXPLORATOR					
21 Heritage in action					
22 ARQUIVO NOVONEYRA					
23 GLAMWiki colloboration					
24 E-Pics and sMapshot					
25 PhD conference					
26 Monument Monitor					
27 Lockdown 2020					

Table 35: Licenses used

Question responses to 'Other' option

	Project/Activity	Other
1	Topotheque	Every donator decides under which license his/her donations shall be published
14	Meitheal Logainm.ie	CC BY-NC
24	E-Pics and sMapshot	CC BY SA 4.0

Additional comments

	Project/Activity	Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your answer?
1	Topotheque	Topotheque has all CC licenses selectable.
5	Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.	At the moment there is no specific license in place. Each individual and/or Institution signs a formal agreement with the Ministry in which they comply in making this content available for open access to the public for use and reuse.
6	Historical press photos	It is possible for users to watch the photos and tag them. They can share the photos on social media, but they are not allowed to download and use them.
13	Meitheal Dúchas.ie	CC-BY-NC 4.0
18	Census 1920	Available from December 1, 2020 on Digitalarkivet.no
23	GLAMWiki collaboration	Wikipedia articles are CC-BY-SA. Wikidata metadata is CC0. Wikimedia Commons media files vary in their licensing, but must be Open - so CC0, CC-BY, CC-BY-SA are the only supported Creative Commons licences. The PD-mark can be used to complement a statement that there is no copyright in the media file, but the claim that something is in the public domain must be explicitly motivated (and based on the relevant jurisdictions).

3.24. Additional information

	Project/Activity	Please provide any additional information that you feel is relevant to your project. We would be interested to hear about challenges faced, sustainability plans etc.
1	Topotheque	Is it interesting for Europeana to use Topotheque as a partner source?
5	Cyprus - Library Digital Plt.	The main goal for the project is to attract as many crowd as possible from all cultural backgrounds. The main challenge is the digitisation costs and the creation of the content which need to be done from professionals so as to provide the right content to the general public and the generations to come.
6	Historical press photos	We don't do any validation of the user tags. One user sometimes corrects another user, but both the wrong and the correct tag will be searchable afterwards. It is a weakness, but the joy of getting easier access to the collection with user tags is bigger than the concern about wrong tags. Most tags are fine and decent.

7	Ajapaik	As the project has been running for more than 9 years we've had and constantly have tons of challenges ;)
13	Meitheal Dúchas.ie	You can have a look at the project here: https://www.duchas.ie/en/meitheal . It has been enormously successful.
15	iesaieties.lv	iesaieties.lv includes different types of crowdsourcing. During several projects, we have experimented with society involvement into knowledge production (such as ethnographic surveying, http://jauta.garamantas.lv/lv/survey/view?survey-id=1344815), transforming the content from one format into another (transcription, http://lv100.garamantas.lv/), submission of new objects (e.g. diaries in the time of pandemics, http://garamantas.lv/en/collection/1415829/Pandemijas-dienasgramatas-2020) and creative crowdsourcing (reciting of poetry https://lasi.literatura.lv/lnb100/lasi-skali/1315682 , interpreting archival musical recordings https://dziedi.garamantas.lv/en). All crowdsourcing initiatives carried out since 2016 have been accompanied by publicity campaigns in cooperation with the largest national media and different organizations which help to reach out. The main challenges include (1) sustainable funding to continue the initiatives also after the end of the project, (2) keep the interest of users and to support a user community, (3) further development of the tools and platform, including also interchangeable data formats c.
19	Giza plateau pyramids	Thanks
23	GLAMWiki collaboration	Just a reminder that this response is based on our GLAMWiki-collaboration work in general. However, if you want to learn more about a specific GLAMwiki-project do check out FindingGLAMs, https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/FindingGLAMs/White_Paper It's recent and also comprises a wide spectrum of GLAMWiki-activities and different types of GLAM-data/collections. A reiteration that the GLAMWiki-movement is global. This survey response is representative of the work carried out by Wikimedia Sverige only.
27	Lockdown 2020	This was a small local initiative run with limited staffing resources available for a short time. We are still accepting contributions but not currently promoting the initiative. We will merge our results with those from other initiatives within the University and the city.

Annex 4: Projects identified through the desk research

Project Title	URL	Country	Project Type	Open to new contributions?	Contact Email
Topothek	https://www.topothek.at/en/	Austria	Historical material – CS	Yes	as@topothek.at
ARC 3D Webservice	https://homes.esat.kuleuven.be/~visit3d/websevice/v2/	Belgium	Reconstruction Tool	Yes	info@arc3d.be
State Archives of Belgium	http://www.arch.be/index.php?!=en&m=genealogist&r=demogen	Belgium	Transcription	Yes	digita@arch.be
Cultural Heritage Reporters – European Solidarity Corps short-term Volunteering projec	https://esc-culturalheritag.wixsite.com/esc-culturalheritage/about , https://iccsbulgaria.wordpress.com/esc-with-iccs/	Bulgaria, Italy	Digital valorization of the cultural heritage	No	iccs.bulgaria@gmail.com
1001 stories of Denmark	http://www.kulturarv.dk/1001fortaellinger/en_GB	Denmark	Mapping/Stories	Yes	web@kum.dk
Danish Family Search	https://www.danishfamilysearch.com/projects/	Denmark	Various (mainly transcription)	Yes	info@danishfamilys earch.dk
Dansk Demografisk Database	https://ddd.dda.dk/deltag.asp	Denmark	Census Archive	Yes	mailboxDDD@sa.dk
Kobenhavns Stadsarkiv	https://www.kbharkiv.dk/sog-i-arkivet/kilder-pa-nettet/politiets-registerblade	Denmark	Transcription	No	stadsarkiv@kff.kk.d k
Rigsarkivet	https://cs.sa.dk/?locale=da	Denmark	Various (mainly transcription)	Yes	crowd@sa.dk
Ajapaik	https://ajapaik.ee/?page=1	Estonia	Photo Archive	Yes	info@ajapaik.ee
Eestlased Esimeses maailmasõjas	http://www.ra.ee/ilmasoda/index.php/site/index	Estonia	Historical Archive	Yes	http://www.ra.ee/il masoda/index.php/ site/contact

My House of European History	https://my-european-history.ep.eu/myhouse/timeline	Europe	Stories/mixed media	Yes	Online form under "Help"
Pluggy	https://pluggy.eu/	Europe	Stories	Yes	info@pluggy-project.eu
WithCrowd	https://withcrowd.eu/en	Europe	Tagging	Yes	withdev@image.ntua.gr
Pericules - Martime Culture Mao	https://www.pericles-heritage.eu/	Europe – some	Mapping	Yes	?
Europeana 1989 Digital Archive!	https://fbc.pionier.net.pl/zbiorki/dlibra?action=ChangeLanguageAction&language=en	Europe – various	Collections	Yes	fbc@lists.man.poznan.pl
#collectingsocialphoto	http://collectingsocialphoto.nordiskamuseet.se/anthology-connect-to-collect/	Finland	Photo Archive/Research Project	No	kajsa.hartig@nordiskamuseet.se
Albumit auki	https://albumitauki.fi/?fbclid=IwAR2-JBBrUIT1xUcUtH-JkqLcWCYsyxEwyUpslNOgOFXCHkSK2NSuSdin9s	Finland	Photo Archive	Yes	info@albumitauki.fi
Elava Perinto - National Inventory of Living Heritage	https://wiki.aineetonkulttuuriperinto.fi/wiki/EI%C3%A4v%C3%A4n_perinn%C3%B6n_kansallinen_luettelo/en	Finland	Wiki Inventory	Yes	aineetonkulttuuriperinto@museovirasto.fi
Kesätapahtumat 2020	https://link.webropolsurveys.com/Participation/Public/01a9e57b-765d-45d6-a0f6-3a00cf161e74?displayId=Fin2013303	Finland	Collection of events (coronavirus related)	Yes	vapaakappale@helsinki.fi
Muistojen Nikkilä (Nikkilä Memories)	https://app.maptionnaire.com/fi/1153/	Finland	Mapping/Stories	No	pilvi.nummi@aalto.fi
Plus/Minus Winter	www.plusmiinustalvi.com	Finland	Photo pairing (Then and now)	Yes	plusmiinustalvi@culturafinland.fi

Projekt Fredrika	https://projektfredrika.fi/bidra/	Finland	Wiki	Yes	info@projektfredrika.fi
Wiki loves monuments	http://kozadat.hu/kereso/	Finland	Photo competition	Yes	http://wlm.wikimedia.fi/yhteys/
Wikidocumentaries (demo phase)	http://wikidocumentaries-demo.wmflabs.org/	Finland	Wiki	No	wikidocumentaries@gmail.com
Archives departementales de la Vendee dictionaries	http://www.archives.vendee.fr/Participer/Dictionnaires-historiques-et-collaboratifs	France	Various	Yes	http://www.archives.vendee.fr/Nous-ecrire/Poser-une-question
Data.Culture.Gouv.Fr	https://data.culturecommunication.gouv.fr/explore/?sort=modified	France	Open data	Yes	https://data.culturecommunication.gouv.fr/pages/contact/
Ephemeris Archives departementales de la Vendee	http://www.archives.vendee.fr/Ephemeres	France	Event reporting	Yes	http://www.archives.vendee.fr/Nous-ecrire/Poser-une-question/
Laboratoire des internautes les archives de la vendee	http://www.laboratoire-archives.vendee.fr/	France	Various	Yes	http://www.laboratoire-archives.vendee.fr/Proposer-une-question
Les herbonautes	http://lesherbonautes.mnhn.fr/	France	Natural history	Yes	veronique@telabotanica.org
Noms de Vendee	http://www.nomsdevendee.fr/	France	Index documents	Yes	http://www.archives.vendee.fr/Nous-ecrire/Poser-une-question/
Artigo	http://www.artigo.org/about.html	Germany	Art tagging	Yes	artigo@artigo.org

Berliner Großstadtgeschichten	http://grosstadtgeschichten-berlin.de/ueber-das-projekt	Germany	Mapping/Stories	Yes	landesbibliothek-digital@zlb.de
City laboratory digital - Frankfurt	https://historisches-museum-frankfurt.de/stadtlabor-digital	Germany	Digital stories -video messages, photo series, audio recordings and statements.	Yes	info.historisches-museum@stadt-frankfurt.de
Interlinking Pictura	https://interlinking.bbf.dipf.de/index.php/Hauptseite	Germany	Various (mainly transcription)	Yes	interlinking@dipf.de
Moravian Lives	http://moravianlives.org/the-moravian-church/	Germany	Transcription	Yes	faull@bucknell.edu
Stadtlabor Digital	https://historisches-museum-frankfurt.de/stadtlabor-digital	Germany	Mapping	Yes	https://historisches-museum-frankfurt.de/de/kontakt
Wir Waren So Frei 1989/1990	https://www.wir-waren-so-frei.de/index.php	Germany	Photo Archive	Yes	info@wir-waren-so-frei.de
Altes Leipzig	http://www.altes-leipzig.de/	Germany	Collecting	Yes	wehlmann@altes-leipzig.de
Archive Alert	https://archivealert.gr/web/about	Greece	Archives/cultural materials	Yes	https://archivealert.gr/web/contact
Hermoupolis Digital Heritage Management (HERMES)	https://hermoupolis.omeka.net/	Greece	Photo/Story	Yes	info@iampavlos.com
Istorima	https://www.istorima.org	Greece	Oral storoes	Yes	info@istorima.org
Digitalis Keparchivum	http://keptar.oszk.hu/indexeng.phtml	Hungary	Photo Archive	Yes	info@huntmuseum.com ?????
Fortepan	https://beta.fortepan.hu/	Hungary	Photo Archive	Yes	fortepan@gmail.com
Magyar Elektronikus Könyvtár	http://mek.oszk.hu/indexeng.phtml	Hungary	Document Archive	Yes	info@mek.oszk.hu

Rabcatorok	https://rabcatorok.interaktiv.pannonhelyitermek.hu/#desc	Hungary	Photo/Document Archive	Yes	info@westpannon.hu
Culture Gate	https://www.culture-gate.com/	International	Mapping	Yes	dkoukopoulos@upatras.gr
History Pin	https://www.historypin.org/en/	International	Photos/Story Archive	Yes	jon.voss@historypin.org
ICOMOS	https://www.icomos.org/en/get-involved/inform-us/donate-photos?fbclid=IwAR36yM6T-6TT5bRYZc8F8H-zedLeXD9AQRqr WEu eD aXPCnDdwG x4yZk	International	Photo Archive	Yes	secretariat@icomos.org
Project Mosul	https://projectmosul.org/locations	International	Mapping	Yes	https://projectmosul.org/contact
ARDNACRUSHA MEMORIES: COLLECTING YOUR STORIES ABOUT THE SHANNON HYDRO-ELECTRIC SCHEME	https://www.huntmuseum.com/2020/05/01/ardnacrusha-memories-collecting-your-stories-about-the-shannon-hydro-electric-scheme/	Ireland	Stories	Yes	info@huntmuseum.com
Clare Memories	http://www.clarememories.ie/	Ireland	Audio Archive	Yes	info@clarememories.ie
Historic Graves	https://historicgraves.com/	Ireland	Photo Archive/Surveying	Yes	https://historicgraves.com/contact/to-request-training
Letters 1916-1923	http://letters1916.maynoothuniversity.ie/wp-post/about%2Fabout-the-project	Ireland	Transcription and uploads	Yes	http://letters1916.maynoothuniversity.ie/
Living in Lockdown: Archives of the Trinity Community in the	https://www.tcd.ie/library/lockdown-living/	Ireland	Stories	Yes	library@tcd.ie

Covid-19 Pandemic 2020					
Meitheal Dúchas.ie: Community Transcription	https://www.duchas.ie/en/info/meitheal	Ireland	Transcription	Yes	eolas@duchas.ie
Meitheal Logainm.ie	https://meitheal.logainm.ie/en/	Ireland	Mapping	Yes	logainm@dcu.ie
Moycullen Heritage	https://moycullen.galwaycommunityheritage.org/	Ireland	Photo Archive/Stories	Yes	moycullenheritage@gmail.com
ArcheoSitarProject	http://www.archeositarproject.it/	Italy	Open data	Yes	archeositarproject@beniculturali.it
Attivazione dei Bacini Culturali Siciliani	https://baciniculturalisiciliani.giscloud.com/	Italy	Mapping	Yes	progetto@baciniculturalisiciliani.eu
Mappi-na	https://www.mappi-na.it/#/	Italy	Mapping	Yes	info@mappi-na.it
Eduards Veidenbaums	https://lasi.literatura.lv/lv/tune/tune/lasi-veidenbaumu?work=1004558	Latvia	Poetry	Yes	lfk@lulfmi.lv
Lets's Read Poems	https://berni.literatura.lv/lasi-skali/1151222	Latvia	Childrens Poetry	Yes	lfk@lulfmi.lv
Sing with the Archives		Latvia	Audio archive. Match old with new	Yes	info@lulfmi.lv
Valodas talka	http://talka.garamantas.lv/	Latvia	Transcription	Yes	garamantas@lulfmi.lv
Wizards of the Century	http://lv100.garamantas.lv/	Latvia	Transcription	Yes	garamantas@lulfmi.lv
BIČIŲ KORYS - Bendruomeni (Bee Hive. Community Ethnography)	https://bendruomeniukrastotyra.lt/	Lithuania	Stories.Photos	Yes	info@bendruomeniukrastotyra.lt

Lingscape	https://lingscape.uni.lu/?fbclid=IwAR0da9FOXSFfqbqIRN22hmuuNOo907no2Pm5ZMq_Lxf3pSgxa nTbpHZdjPI	Luxembourg	Mapping/Language	Yes	https://lingscape.uni.lu/?fbclid=IwAR0da9FOXSFfqbqIRN22hmuuNOo907no2Pm5ZMq_Lxf3pSgxa nTbpHZdjPI
Captions for Cas	https://www.nederlandsfotomuseum.nl/captions-for-cas/	Netherlands	Photo captions	Yes	https://www.nederlandsfotomuseum.nl/contact/
Geheugen van Oost (Memories of the East). Also links to other areas	http://www.geheugenvanoost.nl/	Netherlands	Intangible heritage, stories	Yes	geheugenvanoost@amsterdammuseum.nl
Heritage Quest	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/evakap/heritag89ie-quest	Netherlands	Citizen Science	No	e.kaptijn@landschapergoedutrecht.nl
Koninklijke Bibliotheek	https://www.meertens.knaw.nl/kranten_editor/	Netherlands	Transcription	Yes	post@nicolinevdsijs.nl
Red Een Portret	http://redeenportret.nl/	Netherlands	Photo recognition	Yes	redeenportret@stadsarchief.amsterdam.nl
VeleHanden	https://velehanden.nl/	Netherlands	Transcription	Yes	info@velehanden.nl
CINE	https://www.cineg.org/	Northern Europe	Mapping	Yes	anna.vermehren@museumnord.no
Digital Arkivet	https://www.digitalarkivet.no/content/contribute	Norway	Transcription	Yes	digitalarkivet@arkivverket.no
Kulturminnesok	https://kulturminnesok.no/	Norway	Mapping/Database	Yes	Kulturminnesok@ra.no
Localhistoriewiki.no	https://lokalhistoriewiki.no/wiki/lokalhistoriewiki.no:Hovedside	Norway	Wiki	Yes	nli@nb.no

Minner	https://minner.no/	Norway	Mapping/Photo Archive/Stories	Yes	audun.kjus@norskfolkemuseum.no
Archiwa Przelomu	http://www.archiwaprzelomu.pl/	Poland	Historical Archive	Yes	http://www.archiwaprzelomu.pl/Napiszdonas,33
SkarbyKorony	https://www.skarbykorony.pl/	Poland	Catalogue of local creators	Yes	gok@chelmiec.pl
Transcribathon 2020 - Wrocław	https://www.facebook.com/events/2701447519976756/	Poland	Transcription event	No	
Explorator	https://coicatalogue.uc.pt/explorator/	Portugal	Citizen Science/Natural History	Yes	coi@bot.uc.pt
Memoria Para Todos	https://memoriaparatodos.pt/portfolio/memorias-de-trazer-por-casa/	Portugal	Photo Archive/Stories	Yes	fernandarollo@netcabo.pt
Conect-e	https://www.conecte.es/index.php/es/guia-de-usuario	Spain	Ecology	Yes	contacto@conecte.es
Conoce Tus Fuentes	http://www.conocetusfuentes.com/home.php	Spain	Mapping/Photo Archive	Yes	lsanchezdiaz@ugr.es
Les Alqueriespèdia!	http://www.lesalqueriespedia.com/tot-arxiu/	Spain	Stories	Yes	lesalqueriespedia@gmail.com
ahotsak.eus - Basque dialects and oral heritage	https://ahotsak.eus/info/	Spain – Basque	Audio, transcription	Yes	https://ahotsak.eus/kontaktua
SOINU MAPA	http://www.soinumapa.net/?lang=en	Spain – Basque	Audio, various	Yes	audiolab.eus@gmail.com
Artportalen	https://www.artportalen.se/	Sweden	Ecology	Yes	artportalen.support@lansstyrelsen.se
Cultural Heritage Norrbotten's Database	http://www.kulturarvnorrbotten.se/ladda-upp/	Sweden	Photo Archives (various)	Yes	info@kulturarvnorrbotten.se

Forskarfredag 2016 Bulletin Board Mass Experiment	https://forskarfredag.se/forskarfredags-massexperiment/anslagstavlan-2016/	Sweden	Mass Experiment	No	fredrik@va.se undeliverable
Minnen	https://minnen.se/	Sweden	Mapping/Photo Archive/Stories	Yes	support@kulturit.no
Stockholm County Museum - Contemporary Picture	https://stockholmslansmuseum.se/samlingar/samling-pagar/samtidsbild/	Sweden	Photo Archive (app)	Yes	lenita.garde@stockholmslansmuseum.se
Aldermaston History	https://www.aldermastonhistory.uk/	UK	Photo/stories archive	Yes	contact.us@aldermastonhistory.uk
American Air Museum in Britain	https://www.americanairmuseum.com/	UK	Photo/stories archive	Yes	https://www.iwm.org.uk/corporate/press?_ga=2.130893455.1420267649.1595245695-1589427752.1593435421
Anno Tate	https://anno.tate.org.uk/#!/	UK	Transcription	No	?
ART UK Tagger (temporarily suspended)	https://artuk.org/about/tagger	UK	Art tagging	No	info@artuk.org
Birmingham Music Archive	https://www.birminghammusicarchive.com/	UK	Music/Story Archive	Yes	https://www.birminghammusicarchive.com/contact-us/
Black Coal Miners - Digging Deep	https://www.blackcoalminers.com/diggingdeep	UK	Photo/stories archive	Yes	info@blackcoalminers.com
British Library - In the Spotlight	https://www.libcrowds.com/collection/playbills	UK	Transcription	Yes	digitalresearch@bl.uk
British Library Georeferencer	http://britishlibrary.georeferencer.com/start	UK	Mapping	Yes	georeferencer@bl.uk

CITiZAN	https://citizan.org.uk/	UK	Mapping/Surveying	Yes	citizan@mola.org.uk k undeliverable
Colourful Heritage	https://www.colourfulheritage.com/	UK	Video Archive	Yes	info@colourfulheritage.com
Community Mapping	https://communitymaps.org.uk/projects	UK	Mapping (several projects)	Yes	info@mappingforchange.org.uk
Francis Frith	https://www.francisfrith.com/	UK	Photo/stories archive	Yes	https://www.francisfrith.com/contact
HAT Ghostsigns	https://www.hatads.org.uk/catalogue/ghostsigns.aspx	UK	Photo Archive	Yes	enquiries@hatads.org.uk
Herefordshire History	https://herefordshirehistory.org.uk/	UK	History Archive	Yes	herefordshirehistory@herefordshire.gov.uk
Heritage Helpers	https://heritagehelpers.co.uk/	UK	Transcription	Yes	info@heritagehelpers.co.uk
Historic Engalnd	https://historicengland.org.uk/listing/enrich-the-list/	UK	Photo Archive	Yes	https://historicengland.org.uk/coronavirus/offices-and-services/
Layers of London	https://www.layersoflondon.org/?fbclid=IwAR2nAhLJNgWgu-how3IKR87RzUBALmsfD9sY9ZZhB0EJGw3la4QiQlty4KI	UK	Mapping/Stories	Yes	layersoflondon@london.ac.uk
Listening Experience Database	https://led.kmi.open.ac.uk/	UK	Experience Database	Yes	fass-listening-experience@open.ac.uk
Lives of the First World War	https://www.iwm.org.uk/projects-partnerships/lives-of-the-first-world-war/general-fags	UK	Stories	No	https://customerportal.iwm.org.uk/contact-iwm/

Maker Memories	http://www.makermemories.org/#portfolioModal1	UK	Photo Archive	Yes	info@makerwithramecic.org.uk
Map the Museum	http://mapthemuseum.org.uk/#14.00/50.8300/-0.1400	UK	Mapping	Yes	objectimages@brighthon-hove.gov.uk
Micropasts	https://crowdsourced.micropasts.org/	UK	Transcription	Yes	info@micropasts.org
Monument Monitor	https://www.monumentmonitor.co.uk/results	UK	Photo Archive	Yes	rosie.brigham.10@ucl.ac.uk
Museum of Oxford City Stories	https://museumofoxford.omeka.net/exhibits/show/the-covid-19-pandemic-and-oxfo/c19	UK	Photo Archive	Yes	https://museumofoxford.omeka.net/contact
Operation War Diary	https://www.operationwardiary.org/#/	UK	Transcription	No	?
Our Heritage TV	https://www.ourheritage.tv/discover	UK	Video/Photo Archive	Yes	https://www.ourheritage.tv/contact
Oxford Lockdown 2020	http://lwf.it.ox.ac.uk/s/lockdown/page/index	UK	Stories	Yes	runcoco@it.ox.ac.uk
People's Collection Wales	https://www.peoplescollection.wales/about-us	UK	Archive	Yes	https://www.peoplescollection.wales/contact-us
Pride of Place Map	https://www.historypin.org/en/prideofplace/geo/53.171753,-3.90698,5/bounds/44.149046,-35.288329,60.628984,27.474369/paging/1	UK	Mapping	Yes	hali.dardar@historypin.org
Shetland Amenity Trust - Place Name Projects	https://www.shetlandamenity.org/become-involved	UK	Placenames	Yes	info@shetlandamenity.org

Sporting Heritage	https://www.sportingheritage.org.uk/content/contribute/add-archive-directory	UK	Photo/Document Archive	Yes	info@sportingheritage.org.uk
Stokes Croft Street Stories (still in development)	https://prsc.org.uk/street-stories/	UK	Audio Archive	Yes	projects@prsc.org.uk
Strandlines	https://www.strandlines.london/	UK	Community stories	Yes	contact@strandlines.london
The Tate - Make your own Imagined Museum	https://www.tate.org.uk/whats-on/tate-liverpool/exhibition/works-know-heart-imagined-museum/make-your-own-imagined-museum	UK	Art	Yes	hello@tate.org.uk
Transcribe Bentham	http://transcribe-bentham.ucl.ac.uk/td/Transcribe_Bentham	UK	Transcription	Yes	transcribe.bentham@ucl.ac.uk
UK Red	http://www.open.ac.uk/Arts/reading/UK/faq.php#contributing	UK	Experience Database	Yes	E.G.C.King@open.ac.uk
What's the Score at the Bodleian?	http://www.whats-the-score.org/	UK	Transcription	Faulty	specialcollections.enquiries@bodleian.ox.ac.uk
Woruldhord	http://poppy.nsms.ox.ac.uk/woruldhord/about	UK	History Archive	Yes	woruldhord@oucs.ox.ac.uk
Canmore	https://canmore.org.uk/contributions	UK – Scotland	Contributions	Yes	archives@hes.scot
Pin-a-tale	http://www.bl.uk/pin-a-tale/pin-a-tale-about.html	UK Channel Islands	Mapping/Stories	No	Customer-Services@bl.uk
Map Warper	https://mapwarper.net/maps	Various	Mapping	Yes	tim@geothings.net
Monasterium (editing only)	https://www.monasterium.net/mom/home	Various	History Archive	Yes	info@monasterium.net

Open Plaques	https://openplaques.org/	Various	Photo Archive	Yes	feedback@openplaques.org
The Megalithic Portal	https://www.megalithic.co.uk/index.php	Various	Mapping	Yes	andy@megalithic.co.uk
Project Title	URL	Country	Project Type	Open to new contributions?	Contact Email
Topothek	https://www.topothek.at/en/	Austria	Historical material - CS	Yes	as@topothek.at
ARC 3D Webservice	https://homes.esat.kuleuven.be/~visitt3d/websevice/v2/	Belgium	Reconstruction Tool	Yes	info@arc3d.be
State Archives of Belgium	http://www.arch.be/index.php?!=en&m=genealogist&r=demogen	Belgium	Transcription	Yes	digita@arch.be
Cultural Heritage Reporters – European Solidarity Corps short-term Volunteering projec	https://esculturalheritag.wixsite.com/esc-culturalheritage/about , https://iccsbulgaria.wordpress.com/esc-with-iccs/	Bulgaria, Italy	Digital valorization of the cultural heritage	No	iccs.bulgaria@gmail.com
1001 stories of Denmark	http://www.kulturarv.dk/1001fortaellinger/en_GB	Denmark	Mapping/Stories	Yes	web@kum.dk
Danish Family Search	https://www.danishfamilysearch.com/projects/	Denmark	Various (mainly transcription)	Yes	info@danishfamilysearch.dk
Dansk Demografisk Database	https://ddd.dda.dk/deltag.asp	Denmark	Census Archive	Yes	mailboxDDD@sa.dk
Kobenhavns Stadsarkiv	https://www.kbharkiv.dk/sog-i-arkivet/kilder-pa-nettet/politiets-registerblade	Denmark	Transcription	No	stadsarkiv@kff.kk.dk
Rigsarkivet	https://cs.sa.dk/?locale=da	Denmark	Various (mainly transcription)	Yes	crowd@sa.dk
Ajapaik	https://ajapaik.ee/?page=1	Estonia	Photo Archive	Yes	info@ajapaik.ee

Eestlased Esimeses maailmasõjas	http://www.ra.ee/ilmasoda/index.php/site/index	Estonia	Historical Archive	Yes	http://www.ra.ee/ilmasoda/index.php/site/contact
My House of European History	https://my-european-history.ep.eu/myhouse/timeline	Europe	Stories/mixed media	Yes	Online form under "Help"
Pluggy	https://pluggy.eu/	Europe	Stories	Yes	info@pluggy-project.eu
WithCrowd	https://withcrowd.eu/en	Europe	Tagging	Yes	withdev@image.ntua.gr
Pericules - Martime Culture Mao	https://www.pericles-heritage.eu/	Europe – some	Mapping	Yes	?
Europeana 1989 Digital Archive!	https://fbc.pionier.net.pl/zbiorki/dlibra?action=ChangeLanguageAction&language=en	Europe – various	Collections	Yes	fbc@lists.man.poznan.pl
#collectingsocialphoto	http://collectingsocialphoto.nordiskamuseet.se/anthology-connect-to-collect/	Finland	Photo Archive/Research Project	No	kajsa.hartig@nordiskamuseet.se
Albumit auki	https://albumitauki.fi/?fbclid=IwAR2-JBBrUIT1xUcUtH-JkqLcWCYsyxEwyUpslNOgOFXCHkSK2NSuSdin9s	Finland	Photo Archive	Yes	info@albumitauki.fi
Elava Perinto - National Inventory of Living Heritage	https://wiki.aineetonkulttuuriperinto.fi/wiki/EI%C3%A4v%C3%A4n_perint%C3%B6n_kansallinen_luettelo/en	Finland	Wiki Inventory	Yes	aineetonkulttuuriperinto@museovirasto.fi
Kesätapahtumat 2020	https://link.webropolsurveys.com/Participation/Public/01a9e57b-765d-45d6-a0f6-3a00cf161e74?displayId=Fin2013303	Finland	Collection of events (coronavirus related)	Yes	vapaakappale@helsinki.fi
Muistojen Nikkilä (Nikkilä Memories)	https://app.maptionnaire.com/fi/1153/	Finland	Mapping/Stories	No	pilvi.nummi@aalto.fi

Plus/Minus Winter	www.plusmiinustalvi.com	Finland	Photo pairing (Then and now)	Yes	plusmiinustalvi@culturafinland.fi
Projekt Fredrika	https://projektfredrika.fi/bidra/	Finland	Wiki	Yes	info@projektfredrika.fi
Wiki loves monuments	http://kozadat.hu/kereso/	Finland	Photo competition	Yes	http://wlm.wikimedia.fi/yhteys/
Wikidocumentaries (demo phase)	http://wikidocumentaries-demo.wmflabs.org/	Finland	Wiki	No	wikidocumentaries@gmail.com
Archives departementales de la Vendee dictionaries	http://www.archives.vendee.fr/Participer/Dictionnaires-historiques-et-collaboratifs	France	Various	Yes	http://www.archives.vendee.fr/Nous-ecrire/Poser-une-question
Data.Culture.Gouv.Fr	https://data.culturecommunication.gouv.fr/explore/?sort=modified	France	Open data	Yes	https://data.culturecommunication.gouv.fr/pages/contact/
Ephemeris Archives departementales de la Vendee	http://www.archives.vendee.fr/Ephemeres	France	Event reporting	Yes	http://www.archives.vendee.fr/Nous-ecrire/Poser-une-question/
Laboratoire des internautes les archives de la vendee	http://www.laboratoire-archives.vendee.fr/	France	Various	Yes	http://www.laboratoire-archives.vendee.fr/Proposer-une-question
Les herbonautes	http://lesherbonautes.mnhn.fr/	France	Natural history	Yes	veronique@telabotanica.org
Noms de Vendee	http://www.nomsdevendee.fr/	France	Index documents	Yes	http://www.archives.vendee.fr/Nous-ecrire/Poser-une-question/

Artigo	http://www.artigo.org/about.html	Germany	Art tagging	Yes	artigo@artigo.org
Berliner Großstadtgeschichten	http://grosstadtgeschichten-berlin.de/ueber-das-projekt	Germany	Mapping/Stories	Yes	landesbibliothek-digital@zlb.de
City laboratory digital - Frankfurt	https://historisches-museum-frankfurt.de/stadtlabor-digital	Germany	Digital stories -video messages, photo series, audio recordings and statements.	Yes	info.historisches-museum@stadt-frankfurt.de
Interlinking Pictura	https://interlinking.bbf.dipf.de/index.php/Hauptseite	Germany	Various (mainly transcription)	Yes	interlinking@dipf.de
Moravian Lives	http://moravianlives.org/the-moravian-church/	Germany	Transcription	Yes	faull@bucknell.edu
Stadtlabor Digital	https://historisches-museum-frankfurt.de/stadtlabor-digital	Germany	Mapping	Yes	https://historisches-museum-frankfurt.de/de/kontakt
Wir Waren So Frei 1989/1990	https://www.wir-waren-so-frei.de/index.php	Germany	Photo Archive	Yes	info@wir-waren-so-frei.de
Altes Leipzig	http://www.altes-leipzig.de/	Germany	Collecting	Yes	wehlmann@altes-leipzig.de
Archive Alert	https://archivealert.gr/web/about	Greece	Archives/cultural materials	Yes	https://archivealert.gr/web/contact
Hermoupolis Digital Heritage Management (HERMES)	https://hermoupolis.omeka.net/	Greece	Photo/Story	Yes	info@iampavlos.com
Istorima	https://www.istorima.org	Greece	Oral storoes	Yes	info@istorima.org
Digitalis Keparchivum	http://keptar.oszk.hu/indexeng.phtml	Hungary	Photo Archive	Yes	info@huntmuseum.com ??????
Fortepan	https://beta.fortepan.hu/	Hungary	Photo Archive	Yes	fortepan@gmail.com

Magyar Elektronikus Könyvtár	http://mek.oszk.hu/indexeng.phtml	Hungary	Document Archive	Yes	info@mek.oszk.hu
Rabcatorok	https://rabicatorok.interaktiv.pannonhelyitermek.hu/#desc	Hungary	Photo/Document Archive	Yes	info@westpannon.hu
Culture Gate	https://www.culture-gate.com/	International	Mapping	Yes	dkoukopoulos@upatras.gr
History Pin	https://www.historypin.org/en/	International	Photos/Story Archive	Yes	jon.voss@historypin.org
ICOMOS	https://www.icomos.org/en/get-involved/inform-us/donate-photos?fbclid=IwAR36yM6T-6TT5bRYZc8F8H-zedLeXD9AQRqr WEu eD aXPCnDdwG x4yZk	International	Photo Archive	Yes	secretariat@icomos.org
Project Mosul	https://projectmosul.org/locations	International	Mapping	Yes	https://projectmosul.org/contact
ARDNACRUSHA MEMORIES: COLLECTING YOUR STORIES ABOUT THE SHANNON HYDRO-ELECTRIC SCHEME	https://www.huntmuseum.com/2020/05/01/ardnacrusha-memories-collecting-your-stories-about-the-shannon-hydro-electric-scheme/	Ireland	Stories	Yes	info@huntmuseum.com
Clare Memories	http://www.clarememories.ie/	Ireland	Audio Archive	Yes	info@clarememories.ie
Historic Graves	https://historicgraves.com/	Ireland	Photo Archive/Surveying	Yes	https://historicgraves.com/contact/to-request-training
Letters 1916-1923	http://letters1916.maynoothuniversity.ie/wp-post/about%2Fabout-the-project	Ireland	Transcription and uploads	Yes	http://letters1916.maynoothuniversity.ie/

Living in Lockdown: Archives of the Trinity Community in the Covid-19 Pandemic 2020	https://www.tcd.ie/library/lockdown-living/	Ireland	Stories	Yes	library@tcd.ie
Meitheal Dúchas.ie: Community Transcription	https://www.duchas.ie/en/info/meitheal	Ireland	Transcription	Yes	eolas@duchas.ie
Meitheal Logainm.ie	https://meitheal.logainm.ie/en/	Ireland	Mapping	Yes	logainm@dcu.ie
Moycullen Heritage	https://moycullen.galwaycommunityheritage.org/	Ireland	Photo Archive/Stories	Yes	moycullenheritage@gmail.com
ArcheoSitarProject	http://www.archeositarproject.it/	Italy	Open data	Yes	archeositarproject@beniculturali.it
Attivazione dei Bacini Culturali Siciliani	https://baciniculturalisiciliani.giscloud.com/	Italy	Mapping	Yes	progetto@baciniculturalisiciliani.eu
Mappi-na	https://www.mappi-na.it/#/	Italy	Mapping	Yes	info@mappi-na.it
Eduards Veidenbaums	https://lasi.literatura.lv/lv/tune/tune/lasi-veidenbaumu?work=1004558	Latvia	Poetry	Yes	lfk@lulfmi.lv - these three email addresses rejected
Lets's Read Poems	https://berni.literatura.lv/lasi-skali/1151222	Latvia	Childrens Poetry	Yes	lfk@lulfmi.lv
Sing with the Archives		Latvia	Audio archive. Match old with new	Yes	info@lulfmi.lv
Valodas talka	http://talka.garamantas.lv/	Latvia	Transcription	Yes	garamantas@lulfmi.lv
Wizards of the Century	http://lv100.garamantas.lv/	Latvia	Transcription	Yes	garamantas@lulfmi.lv
BIČIŲ KORYS - Bendruomeni (Bee	https://bendruomeniukrastotyra.lt/	Lithuania	Stories.Photos	Yes	info@bendruomeniukrastotyra.lt

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Ethnography)

Lingscape	https://lingscape.uni.lu/?fbclid=IwAR0da9FOXSFfqbqIRN22hmuuNOo907no2Pm5ZMq_Lxf3pSgxa nTbpHZdjPI	Luxembourg	Mapping/Language	Yes	https://lingscape.uni.lu/?fbclid=IwAR0da9FOXSFfqbqIRN22hmuuNOo907no2Pm5ZMq_Lxf3pSgxa nTbpHZdjPI
Captions for Cas	https://www.nederlandsfotomuseum.nl/captions-for-cas/	Netherlands	Photo captions	Yes	https://www.nederlandsfotomuseum.nl/contact/
Geheugen van Oost (Memories of the East). Also links to other areas	http://www.geheugenvanoost.nl/	Netherlands	Intangible heritage, stories	Yes	geheugenvanoost@amsterdammuseum.nl
Heritage Quest	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/evakap/heritage-quest	Netherlands	Citizen Science	No	e.kaptijn@landschapergoedutrecht.nl
Koninklijke Bibliotheek	https://www.meertens.knaw.nl/kranten_editor/	Netherlands	Transcription	Yes	post@nicolinevdsijs.nl
Red Een Portret	http://redeenportret.nl/	Netherlands	Photo recognition	Yes	redeenportret@stadsarchief.amsterdam.nl
VeleHanden	https://velehanden.nl/	Netherlands	Transcription	Yes	info@velehanden.nl
CINE	https://www.cineg.org/	Northern Europe	Mapping	Yes	anna.vermehren@museumnord.no
Digital Arkivet	https://www.digitalarkivet.no/content/contribute	Norway	Transcription	Yes	digitalarkivet@arkivverket.no
Kulturminnesok	https://kulturminnesok.no/	Norway	Mapping/Database	Yes	Kulturminnesok@ra.no

Localhistoriewiki.no	https://lokalhistoriewiki.no/wiki/lokalhistoriewiki.no:Hovedside	Norway	Wiki	Yes	nli@nb.no
Minner	https://minner.no/	Norway	Mapping/Photo Archive/Stories	Yes	audun.kjus@norskfolkemuseum.no
Archiwa Przelomu	http://www.archiwaprzelomu.pl/	Poland	Historical Archive	Yes	http://www.archiwaprzelomu.pl/Napiszdonas,33
SkarbyKorony	https://www.skarbykorony.pl/	Poland	Catalogue of local creators	Yes	gok@chelmiec.pl
Transcribathon 2020 - Wrocław	https://www.facebook.com/events/2701447519976756/	Poland	Transcription event	No	
Explorator	https://coicatalogue.uc.pt/explorator/	Portugal	Citizen Science/Natural History	Yes	coi@bot.uc.pt
Memoria Para Todos	https://memoriaparatodos.pt/portfolio/memorias-de-trazer-por-casa/	Portugal	Photo Archive/Stories	Yes	fernandarollo@netcabo.pt
Conect-e	https://www.conecte.es/index.php/es/guia-de-usuario	Spain	Ecology	Yes	contacto@conecte.es
Conoce Tus Fuentes	http://www.conocetusfuentes.com/home.php	Spain	Mapping/Photo Archive	Yes	lsanchezdiaz@ugr.es
Les Alqueriespèdia!	http://www.lesalqueriespedia.com/tot-arxiu/	Spain	Stories	Yes	lesalqueriespedia@gmail.com
ahotsak.eus - Basque dialects and oral heritage	https://ahotsak.eus/info/	Spain – Basque	Audio, transcripion	Yes	https://ahotsak.eus/kontaktua
SOINU MAPA	http://www.soinumapa.net/?lang=en	Spain – Basque	Audio, various	Yes	audiolab.eus@gmail.com
Artportalen	https://www.artportalen.se/	Sweden	Ecology	Yes	artportalen.support@lansstyrelsen.se

Cultural Heritage Norrbotten's Database	http://www.kulturarvnorrbotten.se/ladda-upp/	Sweden	Photo Archives (various)	Yes	info@kulturarvnorrbotten.se
Forskarfredag 2016 Bulletin Board Mass Experiment	https://forskarfredag.se/forskarfredags-massexperiment/anslagstavlan-2016/	Sweden	Mass Experiment	No	fredrik@va.se undeliverable
Minnen	https://minnen.se/	Sweden	Mapping/Photo Archive/Stories	Yes	support@kulturit.no
Stockholm County Museum - Contemporary Picture	https://stockholmslansmuseum.se/samlingar/samling-pagar/samtidsbild/	Sweden	Photo Archive (app)	Yes	lenita.garde@stockholmslansmuseum.se
Aldermaston History	https://www.aldermastonhistory.uk/	UK	Photo/stories archive	Yes	contact.us@aldermastonhistory.uk
American Air Museum in Britain	https://www.americanairmuseum.com/	UK	Photo/stories archive	Yes	https://www.iwm.org.uk/corporate/press?_ga=2.130893455.1420267649.1595245695-1589427752.1593435421
Anno Tate	https://anno.tate.org.uk/#!/	UK	Transcription	No	?
ART UK Tagger (temporarily suspended)	https://artuk.org/about/tagger	UK	Art tagging	No	info@artuk.org
Birmingham Music Archive	https://www.birminghammusicarchive.com/	UK	Music/Story Archive	Yes	https://www.birminghammusicarchive.com/contact-us/
Black Coal Miners - Digging Deep	https://www.blackcoalminers.com/diggingdeep	UK	Photo/stories archive	Yes	info@blackcoalminers.com

British Library - In the Spotlight	https://www.libcrowds.com/collection/playbills	UK	Transcription	Yes	digitalresearch@bl.uk
British Library Georeferencer	http://britishlibrary.georeferencer.com/start	UK	Mapping	Yes	georeferencer@bl.uk
CITIZAN	https://citizan.org.uk/	UK	Mapping/Surveying	Yes	citizan@mola.org.uk undeliverable
Colourful Heritage	https://www.colourfulheritage.com/	UK	Video Archive	Yes	info@colourfulheritage.com
Community Mapping	https://communitymaps.org.uk/projects	UK	Mapping (several projects)	Yes	info@mappingforchange.org.uk
Francis Frith	https://www.francisfrith.com/	UK	Photo/stories archive	Yes	https://www.francisfrith.com/contact
HAT Ghostsigns	https://www.hatads.org.uk/catalogue/ghostsigns.aspx	UK	Photo Archive	Yes	enquiries@hatads.org.uk
Herefordshire History	https://herefordshirehistory.org.uk/	UK	History Archive	Yes	herefordshirehistory@herefordshire.gov.uk
Heritage Helpers	https://heritagehelpers.co.uk/	UK	Transcription	Yes	info@heritagehelpers.co.uk
Historic England	https://historicengland.org.uk/listing/enrich-the-list/	UK	Photo Archive	Yes	https://historicengland.org.uk/coronavirus/offices-and-services/
Layers of London	https://www.layersoflondon.org/?fbclid=IwAR2nAhLJNgWgu-how3IKR87RzUBALmsfD9sY9ZZhB0EJGw3la4QjQlty4KI	UK	Mapping/Stories	Yes	layersoflondon@london.ac.uk
Listening Experience Database	https://led.kmi.open.ac.uk/	UK	Experience Database	Yes	fass-listening-experience@open.ac.uk

Lives of the First World War	https://www.iwm.org.uk/projects-partnerships/lives-of-the-first-world-war/general-fags	UK	Stories	No	https://customerportal.iwm.org.uk/contact-iwm/
Maker Memories	http://www.makermemories.org/#portfolioModal1	UK	Photo Archive	Yes	info@makerwithramedic.org.uk
Map the Museum	http://mapthemuseum.org.uk/#14.00/50.8300/-0.1400	UK	Mapping	Yes	objectimages@brighton-hove.gov.uk
Micropasts	https://crowdsourced.micropasts.org/	UK	Transcription	Yes	info@micropasts.org
Monument Monitor	https://www.monumentmonitor.co.uk/results	UK	Photo Archive	Yes	rosie.brigham.10@ucl.ac.uk
Museum of Oxford City Stories	https://museumofoxford.omeka.net/exhibits/show/the-covid-19-pandemic-and-oxfo/c19	UK	Photo Archive	Yes	https://museumofoxford.omeka.net/contact
Operation War Diary	https://www.operationwardiary.org/#/	UK	Transcription	No	?
Our Heritage TV	https://www.ourheritage.tv/discover	UK	Video/Photo Archive	Yes	https://www.ourheritage.tv/contact
Oxford Lockdown 2020	http://lwf.it.ox.ac.uk/s/lockdown/page/index	UK	Stories	Yes	runcoco@it.ox.ac.uk
People's Collection Wales	https://www.peoplescollection.wales/about-us	UK	Archive	Yes	https://www.peoplescollection.wales/contact-us
Pride of Place Map	https://www.historypin.org/en/prideofplace/geo/53.171753,-3.90698,5/bounds/44.149046,-35.288329,60.628984,27.474369/paging/1	UK	Mapping	Yes	hali.dardar@historypin.org

Shetland Amenity Trust - Place Name Projects	https://www.shetlandamenity.org/come-involved	UK	Placenames	Yes	info@shetlandamenity.org
Sporting Heritage	https://www.sportingheritage.org.uk/content/contribute/add-archive-directory	UK	Photo/Document Archive	Yes	info@sportingheritage.org.uk
Stokes Croft Street Stories (still in development)	https://prsc.org.uk/street-stories/	UK	Audio Archive	Yes	projects@prsc.org.uk
Strandlines	https://www.strandlines.london/	UK	Community stories	Yes	contact@strandlines.london
The Tate - Make your own Imagined Museum	https://www.tate.org.uk/whats-on/tate-liverpool/exhibition/works-know-heart-imagined-museum/make-your-own-imagined-museum	UK	Art	Yes	hello@tate.org.uk
Transcribe Bentham	http://transcribe-bentham.ucl.ac.uk/td/Transcribe_Bentham	UK	Transcription	Yes	transcribe.bentham@ucl.ac.uk
UK Red	http://www.open.ac.uk/Arts/reading/UK/faq.php#contributing	UK	Experience Database	Yes	E.G.C.King@open.ac.uk
What's the Score at the Bodleian?	http://www.whats-the-score.org/	UK	Transcription	Faulty	specialcollections.enquiries@bodleian.ox.ac.uk
Worldhord	http://poppy.nsms.ox.ac.uk/worldhord/about	UK	History Archive	Yes	woruldhord@oucs.ox.ac.uk
Canmore	https://canmore.org.uk/contributions	UK – Scotland	Contributions	Yes	archives@hes.scot
Pin-a-tale	http://www.bl.uk/pin-a-tale/pin-a-tale-about.html	UK Channel Islands	Mapping/Stories	No	Customer-Services@bl.uk
Map Warper	https://mapwarper.net/maps	Various	Mapping	Yes	tim@geothings.net

Monasterium (editing only)	https://www.monasterium.net/mom/home	Various	History Archive	Yes	info@monasterium.net
Open Plaques	https://openplaques.org/	Various	Photo Archive	Yes	feedback@openplaques.org
The Megalithic Portal	https://www.megalithic.co.uk/index.php	Various	Mapping	Yes	andy@megalithic.co.uk